

Data Management Guidance Document

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Northern European Atlantic

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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	4
List of Figures	5
List of Tables.....	5
Acronyms	6
About SIMNORAT	7
Introduction.....	8
Part 1. SIMNORAT Data Portal	10
1. Objectives	10
2. Architecture.....	12
3. Interface and Functionalities.....	14
4. Technical Requirements.....	15
4.1. Inspire compliance.....	15
4.2. Licenses	20
Part 2. SIMNORAT Data Portal Administration Processes	22
1. Geonetwork.....	23
2. Geoserver	36
3. Map Viewer.....	46
Part 3. Challenges	52
Conclusion	59
Annex 1: List of Sources.....	61

List of Figures

Figure 1: SIMNORAT Data Portal	10
Figure 2: SIMNORAT Data Portal Concepts and Answers	11
Figure 3: SDP technical infrastructure	12
Figure 4: Geoserver Harvesting Process	12
Figure 5: Metadata Harvesting Concept	13
Figure 6: SIMNORAT Data Portal Interface	14
Figure 7: Collect Once, Use Many Times	17
Figure 8: Web Services requests (examples)	18
Figure 9: Data Web Services	19
Figure 10: Catalogue Service for the Web	19
Figure 11: Web Processing Services	20
Figure 12: Geonetwork Processes	23
Figure 13: Technical Sheet Components	24
Figure 14: Geoserver Processes	36
Figure 15: Map Viewer Processes	46
Figure 16: Sheet reading guide	53

List of Tables

Table 1: SIMCelt Data portal Main Functionalities	15
Table 2: Technical Sheets Action Icons	25

Acronyms

AAMP: Agence des Aires Marines Protégées
AFB: Agence Française pour la Biodiversité (previously AAMP)
ArcSDE: Spatial Database Engine (produced and marketed by Esri)
CSW: Catalogue service for the web
CRS: Coordinate Reference System
DG Mare: Directorate General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
EMODnet: European Marine Observation and Data Network
FTL: Free Marker Template
GIS: Geographic Information System
GML: Geography Markup Language
HTTP: HyperText Transfer Protocol
IHO: International Hydrographic Organisation
INSPIRE: Infrastructure for spatial information in Europe
ISO: International Organisation for Standardisation
KML: Keyhole Markup Language
MMO: Marine Management Organisation
MPA : Marine protected area
MSDI: Marine Spatial Data Infrastructure
MSP: Maritime Spatial Planning
OGC: Open geospatial Consortium
OSPAR: OSLO-Paris Convention (for protection and conservation of North-East Atlantic)
PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor
SDI: Spatial Data Infrastructure
SLD: Styled Layer Descriptor
SDP: SIMNORAT Data Portal
Shom: French public establishment in charge of description and forecasting of ocean, from littoral to offshore
SIMCelt: Supporting Implementation of Maritime Spatial Planning in the Celtic Seas
SIMNORAT: Supporting Implementation of Maritime Spatial Planning in the Northern European Atlantic
SIMWESTMED: Supporting Implementation of Maritime Spatial Planning in the Western Mediterranean Region
SLD: Style Layer Descriptor
SOAP: Simple Object Access Protocol
UKHO: United Kingdom Hydrographic Office
URL: Uniform Resource Locator
WCS: Web Coverage Service
WFS: Web Feature Service
WMS: Web Map Service
WMTS: Web Map Tile Service
WPS: Web processing service
XML: Extensible Markup Language

About SIMNORAT

Supporting Implementation of Maritime Spatial Planning in the Northern Atlantic region (SIMNORAT) is a two years project co-financed by the DG Mare EMFF Funds. The two-year project began in January 2017. It focuses on supporting the implementation of the European Directive 2014/89/EU, called Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) Directive, and developing concrete cross-border cooperation for MSP between Member States. Led by Shom, the project consortium comprises both planners and researchers from eleven public bodies, from France, Portugal and Spain and international organisations. This consortium is particularly interested in developing meaningful cooperation between neighbouring Member States to support implementation of spatially coherent plans across transboundary zones of the Northern Atlantic, building on previous work and leveraging new opportunities to identify and share best practice on technical, scientific and social aspects of transboundary MSP.

Introduction

The implementation of Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP), defined in the MSP Directive 2014/89/EU requires high quality maritime spatial data and information. Data sharing is favoured by Maritime Spatial Data Infrastructures (MSDI). This type of infrastructure improves access to data and provides information on the MSP policies implemented in the neighbouring countries. MSDIs contribute to enable access to data and information. It is a basis for discussion and exchange and promotes cross-border cooperation.

Regarding environmental data, the INSPIRE Directive was published in 2007 by the European Commission in order to create a European Spatial Data Infrastructure to ensure interoperability between databases and to facilitate geographic data dissemination, availability and use. It provides standards and protocols to exchange data and metadata across Europe. MSP is taking advantage of this conducive environment as over the last few years the amount of available datasets has been constantly increasing, published by national producers as well as European projects (e.g. EMODnet). Despite this fact, some key data and information are not accessible yet. There is therefore a need to pursue the effort on data sharing, as well as providing clear information on data through INSPIRE metadata.

In this European framework, technical requirements for data and information to implement MSP in a transboundary context, especially regarding interoperability, are investigated, specifically in the Northern Atlantic under the SIMNORAT project. The “Data and Information Requirements for MSP” component, led by Shom, is a technical study to identify, analyse and address technical challenges and gaps in data and information, encountered when displaying and disseminating relevant Maritime Spatial Planning data on both sides of maritime boundary. This component involves marine planners and experts of Geospatial data, working together in SIMNORAT Task Group on Data. To achieve these objectives, not only data and information requirements for MSP were examined, but also the actual situation of Marine Spatial Data Infrastructures in order to determine optimisation possibilities. A special interest has been given on interoperability regarding metadata, data and portals, and Web Services availability for transboundary MSP. This study led to produce two main deliverables:

- Analysis of Data Needs and Existing Gaps – Specifically Relating to Transboundary Context ;
- Data Management Guidance Document.

The “Analysis of Data Needs and Existing Gaps – Specifically Relating to Transboundary Context” report describes the state of current data needs and gaps linked to MSP in a transboundary context. It is based on an inventory of datasets selected because they met a series of technical requirements identified by the Task Group on Data, particularly regarding interoperability. Therefore the objective is not to realise an exhaustive data collection, but to point out the relevant datasets in order to give an overview of the data situation in the Northern Atlantic area in terms of availability and interoperability. This panorama allows highlighting the main challenges and opportunities linked to transboundary data interoperability.

The second deliverable, called “Data Management Guidance Document” is the subject of this report. It aims to build up on SIMNORAT experience by sharing technical knowledge and processes required to set up and manage a data portal like SIMNORAT demonstrator. The idea is to allow users to set up software components to develop SDI using open-source tools. Therefore the Data Management Guidance Document describes SIMNORAT data portal infrastructure and its administration procedures. It focuses on challenges encountered and solutions to overcome them.

This document is divided into three parts. Firstly, the description of the data portal demonstrator

architecture and its major functionalities are described. Then the different processes implemented to build this infrastructure are detailed. Finally, an analysis of gaps and possible solutions to overcome them will be provided.

Part 1. SIMNORAT Data Portal

1. Objectives

As part of SIMNORAT project, Shom was in charge of setting up a data portal as a demonstrator to share transboundary MSP Knowledge on the Northern Atlantic area. It is also a decision support tool designed for different audiences:

- GIS experts or data experts to experiment datasets interoperability and to address needs and gaps ;
- All the stakeholders involved in the MSP to display and to use datasets in transboundary context.

In order to improve the browsing experience for such a diverse audience, a specific effort was made on visual appearance to build up a portal as user-friendly as possible.

Figure 1: SIMNORAT Data Portal

SDP is also meant to serve as a technical environment dedicated to identifying data gaps and possible solutions to overcome them in support of the “Data and Information Requirements for MSP” Component. It is used to experiment and improve interoperability between datasets coming from different producers or countries, provided through various protocols or formats, represented with different symbologies, and containing heterogeneous attribute information. There are therefore no intentions either to constitute an exhaustive data catalogue or to maintain the portal after the end of SIMNORAT project.

Another guiding idea when building SIMNORAT Data portal was to ensure that an organisation willing to replicate it would be able to. In order to achieve this goal, only components either under open-source licenses or already developed through other European projects were used. If it has been sometimes occasion to add new functionalities to these existing tools, no new developments from scratch have been led during SIMNORAT project.

Last but not least, a choice was made to build the portal data catalogue by focusing on INSPIRE

web services. This brings several benefits:

- Data is stored by the producer. It avoids unnecessary duplication and lowers the administration processes ;
- Latest available data are always displayed, without any additional manipulation.

The following figure explains the concepts developed by this portal demonstrator and the associated technical answers.

Figure 2: SIMNORAT Data Portal Concepts and Answers

2. Architecture

SIMNORAT Data Portal is based on a spatial data infrastructure (SDI). This SDI is made up of four components.

Figure 3: SDP technical infrastructure

- The metadata catalogue:** The metadata catalogue is used for the publication of information on data like its producers or date of creation. The open-source application Geonetwork 3.0.2 has been chosen in SIMNORAT project. SIMNORAT metadata catalogue gathers metadata records associated with all the datasets relevant for MSP in the Northern Atlantic which are INSPIRE compliant. Although it hosts some metadata records locally, the major part is harvested from external catalogues.
- The geospatial data server:** this component allows publishing geographical data on the web through OGC protocols. If in most cases, its vocation is to spread data (either vector or raster) stored on a local server, it was used in a different way in SIMNORAT project. Experimentations were led to make this tool act as an intermediate between producers' data infrastructures and SIMNORAT Map Viewer, by directly connecting to the partners' web services. The Open-source software Geoserver 2.8 is used for this task.

Figure 4: Geoserver Harvesting Process

The harvesting concept

The harvesting concept can be summarised as “collect once, use many times”. Metadata available in SIMNORAT catalogue are created either in SIMNORAT Geonetwork or in external catalogues.

Indeed, as illustrated on Figure 5, metadata catalogues can communicate with each other; SIMNORAT Data Portal can gather and disseminate metadata from external catalogues. External metadata can be grouped in virtual nodes. SIMNORAT Demonstrator can request these nodes to harvest, and then disseminate external metadata. If necessary, only one part of external catalogue node can be harvested: SIMNORAT administrator can filter metadata harvested from a node: For example, the <http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/> node counts 88 parent metadata and above 20000 metadata. If the request is “all the metadata where the title is “cable”, 2 metadata are harvested.

SIMNORAT metadata can be gathered into one or many nodes in order to be harvested by external metadata or consulted by external users.

Figure 5: Metadata Harvesting Concept

- **Map Viewer (front end):** It is the main access point to SIMNORAT Data Portal. It is an interactive mapping application connected to the metadata catalogue and to the geospatial data server. It

allows displaying selected data together on a map. It also has some specific features like a preconfigured map catalogue, drawing tools and time series. The Map Viewer is developed by a private subcontractor, based on the viewer previously used in EMODnet Coastal Mapping project. Its use is described in the part two of this document for information. The detailed technical elements are specific to this map viewer. Therefore, the process implementation has to be adapted according to the viewer used.

- **Web Processing Service (WPS) Server:** This component is dedicated to publish tools as Web Services. In this way, it is possible to use those tools directly from a web browser or any GIS desktop application able to read WPS protocol (such as QGIS).

3. Interface and Functionalities

SIMNORAT Data portal interface has been thought out to leave to the map as much space as possible, in order to improve user comfort. It includes basic features from geoportals like navigation tools as well as more advanced tools. The scheme below details different components of this interface.

Figure 6: SIMNORAT Data Portal Interface

A number of specific features are dedicated to displaying spatial maritime data in a cross-border area, as the map catalogue. The table below summarises the main user functionalities of SIMNORAT portal.

	Basic features: Map navigation, consult data and metadata, export a map, customisation (projection, language, interface)
	Responsive design: Most of the SDP functionalities are optimised to be displayed in different types of devices (computer, phone...)
	Data catalogue: all the datasets available on the SDP, organised by category. A search box can be used to filter datasets by name. WMS / WFS / KML layers can be imported in the SDP.

	Map Catalogue: set of pre-configured maps (with selected layers, zoom level and geographic extent) on a specific subject or areas.
	SIMNORAT dashboard: hideable panel with information like help for navigation and last updates on the SDP.
Time series: tool for exploring datasets varying over time (see schema below).	
	Drawing tools: set of tools for adding custom graphic objects to the map. The drawing can be exported / imported in KML format and printed as a PDF document.
	Search by location: search box for locating a place by entering its name.
	Bathymetry calculator: Calculate automatically bathymetric depth by moving the navigation cursor on the map.

Table 1: SIMNORAT Data portal Main Functionalities

4. Technical Requirements

The data catalogue constituted in SDP is mostly based on the data selection from the Analysis of Data Needs and Gaps Report . This list of datasets organised by category and sub-category are available in appendix. Each dataset has been first examined independently according to a set of technical criteria. Then all the datasets belonging to the same category have been studied together, in order to keep the best available datasets.

Below are the technical criteria used to select the datasets integrated in SIMNORAT Data Portal.

- Only spatial datasets **relevant for the MSP in a transboundary context** have been considered ;
- When possible chosen datasets **cover the whole project area** or at least Portugal, Spain or France. The goal was to ensure a minimal level of consistency across the project area ;
- **partners data** were favoured because they could beneficiate of time commitment for data harmonisation ;
- Priority was given to **datasets needed for Case studies** to support work in these regions ;
- SIMNORAT data demonstrator uses as much **official data** as possible ;
- Priority was given to **datasets that are OGC and INSPIRE compliant** regarding particularly **metadata** format and contents. Data must also be available in **Web Services** because these do not require storage, guarantee access to the most up-to-date version, and avoid duplicating the maintenance work done by the data producer.
- In terms of **data licensing**, SIMNORAT inventory distinguishes open, shared and closed datasets. As far as possible open data was favoured.

4.1. Inspire compliance

The harmonisation of exchange protocols at European scale facilitates the implementation of the Web Services. Indeed, the INSPIRE Directive 2007/2/EC issued on March 14th, 2007 established an Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European community in order to favour the protection of the environment.

This Directive requires public authorities to publish their geographical environmental data and services on the Web and to share them. The objective is to favour dissemination, availability, quality, accessibility, use and reuse of geographical data and services at European scale. The INSPIRE directive

aims to organise the data opening and the availability by relying on the infrastructures of the Member States so that users and decision-makers can easily have access to reliable geographical information.

The INSPIRE Directive builds on several principles:

- Geographic data must be collected once (to avoid duplication and storage) and be provided and updated by the competent authority.
- It must be possible to combine easily information from heterogeneous source and disseminate them.
- The information collected by public authority that are within the INSPIRE Directive framework must be shared to all other public bodies.
- Geographical information must be available for an extensive use.
- It must be easy to know what information is available, what needs it can meet and under what conditions it can be acquired and used.

As a result, public data producers have to produce as much as possible data and services that respect these principles, which is referred to as INSPIRE compliant data.

Therefore, in this Directive and regarding Data and Information Requirements for MSP component, the main elements that influence the data selected in the inventory are metadata and discovery, displaying and download services. The interest brings especially on the Web Services technology.

4.1.1. Metadata

The INSPIRE Directive aims to ensure the interoperability between databases. Inspire compliance of metadata involves standardisation of datasets and services description.

Metadata aims to describe datasets associated producer, date of production, access constraints and how were they created and why...Metadata interest is to ensure the reliability and the good use of data. Completed metadata improves the referencing and therefore the sharing of the datasets.

Guidelines have been prepared to support public authorities in the establishment of the directive. These documents explain how to write metadata and how to manage metadata catalogues. Indeed, the directive relies on ISO standards (ISO 19115 and ISO 19139) for metadata elaboration of data and services. The requirements concern both the container and the contents of the metadata records.

4.1.2. OGC Web Services

What is it about?

A Web Service is a protocol dedicated to exchanging data between heterogeneous computer systems and applications. Data is prepared in a standardised format in order to be understandable by the receiving system and read on the fly. This way of sharing and accessing data brings several advantages:

- enhanced interoperability,
- Possibility to always access to the most up-to-date data

As far as spatial data is concerned, specific interoperable web services have been adopted, supported by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC). They allow the exchange of data, metadata and processes. In the European Union, the Inspire Directive sets OGC web services as the standard for sharing geographic data.

Why focusing on web services?

“Collect once, use many”: There are plenty of MSP data producers at different scales (from local to

world scale). But how to ensure that data used in the portal is the latest available version and has not been transformed? Web Services follow the paradigm “collect once, use many”.

Data is published from the producer database. It can be used and reused remotely at the same time by several clients/users. Users can gain access to this data by a Web Service protocol (WMS, WFS). If a change occurs in the producer database, data sent by Web Service protocol will also change.

- In a transboundary context, Web Services bring the following advantages:
- To improve interoperability by facilitating the dissemination, the availability to use, or reuse the information
- To ensure that the most up-to-date published datasets are being used
- To improve the skills of sharing and collaborative work
- To avoid storing data in each user server / computer. Only Web Services Requests are stored

Figure 7: Collect Once, Use Many Times

How does it work?

OGC web services allow exchanging data through HTTP protocol. In practice, a client will send to the server an URL containing the request to the server, in order to get back a response. This response will usually be structured in XML format, but can also be an image output for example. Every web service comprises a GetCapabilities operation, which will inform on the requests that can be sent to the server.

Figure 8: Web Services requests (examples)

A Web Services Typology

In geomatics, Web Services are normalised because they use XML and HTTP standards to exchange data according to international and standardised protocols of the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC). Indeed, the syntax of the requests and responses needs to be consistent and thoroughly described. The Web services represent an efficient and fast way of sharing.

According to specifications of the OGC, the web services can belong to three categories that are either data services or metadata services or processing services.

Indeed, OGC has produced a series of specifications for GIS web services named in the format “Web ___ Service” either for simple map display or to manipulate geographical objects or for remote processing.

The web services provide data from several data stores like vector (shapefile, ArcSDE...) and raster (Geotiff, JPG or PNG...).

The present paragraph gathers Web Services into 3 categories:

- Data Web Services
- Metadata Web services
- Processes Web Services

4.1.2.1. Data Web Services

The most commonly encountered data Web Services (WMS, WFS, WCS and WMTS) are listed below:

- Web Feature Service (WFS): WFS corresponds to the download service for vector datasets in INSPIRE terminology. It gives access to the whole features of a dataset, including the attribute table. The standard format for downloading data is the GML (Geography Markup Language), which is a variation of XML dedicated to geographical datasets, but it is also possible to select other output formats.

- **Web Coverage Service (WCS):** WCS is similar to WFS, but is specific for raster datasets (e.g. elevation data). As such, it provides features like multi-band support.
- **Web Map Service (WMS):** WMS is a service for displaying geographic data. Requested datasets are returned as a georeferenced map. WMS requests allow to set many parameters such as extent, display style, or coordinates reference system. In some cases it is also possible to get the feature information by clicking on an object on the map.
- **Web Map Tile Service (WMTS):** WMTS is similar to WMS, with one major difference: it generates the response by using tiles. This enhances the display speed but reduces flexibility and does not allow as many operations on data as WMS.

Figure 9: Data Web Services

4.1.2.2. Metadata Web Services

The Catalogue Service for the Web is a web service dedicated to metadata publication. It allows a metadata catalogue to be harvested by another catalogue or application. Harvesting can be done on all the metadata records present in the catalogue, or based on research criteria (title, keyword, etc.). CSW also offers the possibility to directly manage metadata (add, delete, etc.).

Figure 10: Catalogue Service for the Web

4.1.2.3. Processes Web Services

WPS is the OGC standard for sharing processes. It is thus possible to execute tools directly on the server, and then to download the result of the process. Input data can also be a WFS or a WCS request.

Figure 11: Web Processing Services

4.2. Licenses

A data licence is meant to protect the intellectual property of a dataset, by defining rules to set how a third-party can make use of it. For example, one may be authorised to publish a dataset on a map, but must cite the producer in the sources, and must request approval for putting it on a web portal. Usually, several elements are defined by a data licence, such as:

- Data usage and distribution
- Data modification
- Commercial and non-commercial exploitation
- Attribution (acknowledging the data source)

The combination of rules applied to these elements leads to a wide range of existing data licenses, from the most permissive to the most restrictive. In order to improve readability, the licenses on data encountered during SIMNORAT project were classified into 3 categories: Open data, shared data and closed data.

4.2.1. Open licenses

Open licenses constitute the most permissive kind in terms of user rights. They were mainly brought by the open source movement, and the idea that data and software should be available for everyone, with the only constraint to cite the origin of data. In practical terms, a user is free to:

- copy, publish, distribute and transmit the Information;
- adapt the Information;
- exploit the Information commercially and non-commercially for example, by combining it with other Information, or by including it in your own product or application.

A user must:

- Acknowledge the data source by including the statement specified by the provider.

Data published under open licenses include several benefits, especially in the public sector:

- It increases its reusability;
- More data openly available means more possibilities to develop innovations;
- Efficiency in public action can be drastically improved by sharing data between organisations;
- Open data brings transparency, and can favour citizens understanding and involvement.

The European Union has been supporting open data in the public sector since 2003 and the Directive 2003/98/EC on the re-use of public sector information, updated in 2013. Most Member States provide to public organisations their own open licence, like the “Licence Ouverte” in France, or the “Open Government Licence” in the United Kingdom.

4.2.2. Shared licenses

Shared licenses include all the licence types with more restrictions than open data licenses, but still authorising to use data in the scope of SIMNORAT. This comprises a wide range of licenses, from ones similar to open data but preventing commercial use to others only specifically shared to SIMNORAT project.

4.2.3. Closed licenses

Finally, some datasets encountered during SIMNORAT project could have been of great interest, but licence restrictions prevented from using them. It is the case for example for a lot of data concerning fishing activity in France.

Part 2. SIMNORAT Data Portal Administration Processes

This second part of this document describes the general organisation and the administration processes for three main components of the architecture: GeoNetwork, GeoServer and the Map Viewer. The aim is to share the technical knowledge and processes required to build up a portal demonstrator, using open tools as far as possible. The description of administrative processes demonstrates the user requirements and steps to set up an SDI using free tools and an existing viewer. Only the viewer is not an open source. This document part focuses on technical problems encountered and solutions to overcome them.

The SDP management processes are presented in the form of technical sheets. They detail the methodology and the tools used. When needed, the sheets focus on gaps and the possible solutions to overcome them. The guide for reading the technical sheet is described below.

1. Geonetwork

One challenge of the SIMNORAT is to experiment with the metadata harvesting process in the SIMNORAT Metadata Catalogue. The open-source catalogue application used is Geonetwork.

The first steps are the creation of a new user (TS1.) and a new group (TS2.). Each user is assigned a profile defining what tasks he can perform on the system or on metadata records. A group of users corresponds to logical units within an organization with specific privileges, like for example data thematic.

Geonetwork catalogue can be populated with 3 different metadata inputs:

- Harvested from an external metadata catalogue (TS3.)
- Imported from an XML file (TS4.)
- Created in the local Geoserver (TS5.).

Then the metadata catalogue is harvestable by external catalogues using the Catalogue Service for the Web. Additional nodes – virtual CSW - can be set by filtering the CSW catalogue (TS6.).

The Geonetwork gives the possibility to publish a metadata or a template (TS7) and to use the template to create new metadata records (Create a template TS8. and Create a metadata from a template-TS9.).

The metadata records harvest or create in the Geonetwork catalogue can be translated by the administrator to ease their comprehension by users (Translate a metadata -TS10).

The following chart illustrates the harvesting process with reference to technical sheets associated with each action.

Figure 12: Geonetwork Processes

How to read the technical sheets

- Technical sheet components

Figure 13: Technical Sheet Components

- Action icons

In the conceptual scheme of technical sheets, several icons are represented. They represent the main actions of the process described in the sheet. They are gathered in the list below with their meaning in the frame of this document.

ICON	ACTION	ICON	ACTION
	Associate objects		
	Test a process		
	Launch a process		
	Preview a layer		
	Copy an object		

Table 2: Technical Sheets Action Icons

- Tags

In processes, some parameters do not affect all data formats. For example, the action to choose a style is only possible for the Web Feature Service and Shapefiles. Therefore to help users, when necessary, tags are used in technical sheets. A tag mentions the specific data format for which the step is required or relevant. The four tags presents in this document are:

 : Web Map Service

 : Shapefile

 : Web Feature Service

 : Geotiff

TS1. Create a group

A Group can contain one or more users with different profiles. A group of users correspond to logical units within an organization for example data thematic. Access privileges can be set per metadata record and also per Group. Privileges can relate to visibility of the Metadata (Publish), data Download, Interactive Map access and display of the record.

Add a new group

- Select the administration button in the menu
- Select users and group menu
- Add new group

Edit the new group parameters :

Customise the new group parameters: This is a non-exhaustive list of parameters to describe:

- Fill the name*
- Summary description
- Category: default category assigned to listings
- Email* to receive feedback on data download about resources that are part of group

Save to finish the process

Choose the user role in each group

TS2. Create a user

The User concept is related to Group concept because a User can be part of one or more Groups and a user can have different roles in different groups. A role or User Profiles defines what tasks the user can perform on the system or on specific metadata records.

Add a new user

- Select the administration button in the menu
- Select users and group menu
- Add new user

Edit the new user parameters

Customise the new user parameters: This is a non-exhaustive list of parameters to describe:

- User name: name to use for identification
- Password, name, surname, organisation, address

Choose the user role in each group

A profile set permission given to user in a group.

- Registered User: he has more access privileges than non-authenticated Guest users like right to download protected data
- Editor: the editor works on metadata like creating/editing/ delete data within the own group
- Content Reviewer: The content reviewer allows to give final clearance on the metadata publication on the Intranet and/or on the Internet
- User Administrator: is the administrator of his/her own group with the privileges like creating or to change users profiles creating editing deleting data
- Administrator: special privileges that give access to all available functions like
 - full rights for creating a new group or users
 - rights to change users/groups profiles
 - full rights for creating, editing, deleting new old metadata
 - perform system administration and configuration tasks

The Administrator Role is not related to a Group

Save to finish the process

TS3. Harvest a CSW Metadata Catalogue

Harvesting is the process of collecting metadata from a remote source and storing it locally in GeoNetwork for a faster search. The process can be configured to launch automatically at regular intervals. It is possible to harvest multiple metadata catalogue types. This sheet details a Catalogue Service for the Web (CSW) metadata catalogue harvesting process. It is an Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standard that allows interaction with one or more resource catalogues. The basic process to harvest a CSW metadata catalogue in SIMNORAT project is described below.

Add a new CSW catalogue

Add a new CSW metadata

- Click on the admin Console button at the top of the page
- Click on the Harvesting menu button
- Choose to harvest from OGC CSW 2.0.2

Edit the harvesting

Complete the harvesting form

This is a non-exhaustive list of parameters to describe in the harvesting form

- Node name and logo***: This is a short description of the remote site. It will be shown in the harvesting main page as the name for this instance of the CSW harvester.
- Group***: A group of users correspond to logical units within an organisation. Populate the group if it already exists. If the group doesn't exist, administrator has to create it first.
- Service URL***: The GetCapabilities URL of the CSW server to be harvested. (eg. <http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/csw-produits>).
- Search filter**: It is possible to filter metadata. If no filter is applied, Geonetwork will harvest all the metadata from the input node.
- Frequency**: This parameter is used to set up an automatic harvesting at regular intervals.

Launch the harvesting

Save parameters

**Mandatory fields*

Launch the harvesting

If the harvesting process runs successfully, the number of metadata records will be displayed in the log part of the harvesting form. This step can be more or less long depending on the number of harvested metadata records and conditions of access to the internet.

TS4. Import a metadata record from XML files

In case metadata external metadata exists in XMS or MEF format but cannot be gathered using CSW file import can be used in Geonetwork. In this technical sheet, it will detail only the process to import an XML files.

Upload a new XML file

- Click on the Contribute menu button at the top of the page
- Click on the “Import new records” button

Edit the form for import sheet

This is not an exhaustive list of parameters and options to import metadata record

- **Source*** : Choose the source of the file – there are 3 possibilities
 - **Upload a file from your computer** :
Select the file : click on the button “select a file” to select the XML in our computer
Specify the file format XML or ZIP/MEF
 - **Copy /paste**: Paste the XML code in the dedicated space as “Metadata contents”
 - **Import a set of files** from a folder on the server
Indicate the directory in which the files are located and specify the file format XML or ZIP/MEF
- **Type of record*** : indicated the type of sheet :
 - **Metadata** : use when loading a normal metadata record
 - **Template**: use when loading a metadata record that will be used as a template to build a new record
 - **Directory entry**: use when loading a set of metadata record
- **Record identifier processing***: to manage potential clashes between ID of metadata records already present in the catalogue and new metadata records
 - **None**: the new ID is left unchanged. If a record already exists with the same ID, an error message will send.
 - **Overwrite metadata with same UUID**: any existing metadata record in the catalogue with the same ID as the new record will be replaced with the metadata record you are loading.
 - **Generate UUID for inserted metadata**: create new a ID for the new metadata records
- **Assign to a Group** : to select a user group in the list to assign to the imported metadata

**Mandatory fields*

Launch the import and check the result

TS5. Create a Metadata Record

Several SIMNORAT metadata associated with dataset can neither be imported nor be gathered from external metadata catalogue. In these cases, users can also create a new metadata record.

Create a new metadata record

- Select Add a new record button in the contribute section
- You can create a metadata from a new dataset, a feature catalogue, a map, a service and other.
- Choose a metadata template among pre-existing or created templates (TS...?), then a group associated with the new metadata record.
- Push the “Create” button to finish the metadata creation process

Edit the new metadata record

Customise in each category metadata fields: A metadata is composed of mandatory (“*” in the metadata sheet) and optional fields, aggregated into entity. This is a non-exhaustive list of entity to describe in the new metadata record form following the pre-existed template for vector data in ISO19139. Users can twist between simple and full view using the button at the top-right of the interface

- Identification info: This section is used to uniquely identify the data. It notably includes the title, contact information, date of the data.
- Spatial representation info: This package describes the mechanism used to represent spatial information.
- Distribution information: Distribution information and process to acquire the datasets.
- Data quality info: This entity provides information about the quality, the sources and the production process of the datasets.
- Reference System Information: Information about spatial and temporal referenced system used in the dataset
- Metadata: This package is used to uniquely identify and describe the metadata.

Save the metadata record to finish the process

Metadata record compliancy is evaluated in a window at the right of the interface.

Preview the metadata record

TS6. Create a virtual Catalogue Service for the Web (CSW)

A CSW gathers all the datasets of a catalogue. It can be composed of several virtual CSW. The virtual CSW is an harvesting node that is a filter set by the administrator on the catalogue CSW (e.g. thematic, metadata type). Using a virtual CSW reduces the harvesting time and improve datasets organisation.

Harvest a CSW Metadata Catalogue (TS3.) and/or import metadata records from XML files (TS6.)

Enable the CSW

- Select the administration button in the menu and then select the CSW button in the parameters menu
- **Enable***: This option allows opening the CSW services. If it is disabled, other catalogues cannot connect to the node using CSW protocol.
- Inserted metadata is public: If this option is checked, all the metadata inserted by CSW will be public.
- Save the CSW process

Create a new virtual CSW

- Select the administration button in the menu then select the parameters menu
- Open virtual CSW menu and click on new virtual CSW

Edit a new virtual CSW

- **Name***: fill the name of this virtual CSW. The format is mandatory as: csw-servicename, where servicename refers to the thematic or the subject of this virtual CSW.
- **Description** : fill a short description of this catalogue
- **Filter(s)***: to create a virtual CSW it is necessary to fill at least a filter of research.
 - Select the filter type: it refers to the title, the keywords or the summary in the metadata record...
 - Write the keyword associated at this filter
 - Specify whether the filter should contain or not contain the keyword
 - Click on this button to add a new filter. It is mandatory to guarantee the record of the previous filter
- **Explicit query section can be used to filter the CSW catalogue using manual request.**
- Save to finish the publishing process.

Test the virtual CSW

Click on CSW test menu and select the CSW to test, then choose a request and send it :

- csw-GetCapabilities. If an answer is returned with the global description then the virtual CSW working
- csw-GetRecord | no filter : The <csw: SearchResults numberOfRecordsMatched> parameters returns the number of records included in this virtual CSW.

TS7. Publish a metadata or a template

By default, a new metadata added in a catalogue is private, only the producer and the administrator have the right to view and modify it. The process of metadata publication is necessary to provide viewing access to a specific group or the public.

TS8. Create a metadata template

Thanks to the use of a template, contributors can create new metadata with a minimum of time. A metadata template contains already set with pre-filled-or not fields.

TS9. Create a metadata record from a template

Thanks to the use of a template, contributors can create new metadata with a minimum of time. A metadata template contains already set with pre-filled-or not fields.

TS10. Translate a metadata record

The INSPIRE metadata template give the possibility to produce easily metadata records in several languages allowing as many people as possible to understand the information.

2. Geoserver

The SIMNORAT technical challenge consists of testing the harvesting and publishing process focusing on WebServices input in Geoserver.

The following chart illustrates the data publication process in Geoserver, referring to corresponding technical sheets.

The creation of a workspace is a necessary first step to organise elements like a store or dataset. Then, “create a store” and “publish a layer” technical sheets describe publication process. WFS or Shape like datasets publication requires style management. The technical sheet 11 “create and publish a style” describes the process implying the generation of an SLD file and its association with one / several layers.

In case an attribute table is associated with a published dataset, the GetFeatureInfo request can be customised using an FTL file as described in the technical sheet 13. SIMNORAT project provides the opportunity to test the publication of raster temporal layers using Geoserver (data sheet 12: “publish a temporal layer”). Then, the Data sheet 10 “publish a layer group” explains the process to gather and organise layers in a hierarchical structure using layer groups.

Figure 14: Geoserver Processes

TS11. Create a Workspace

This section describes how to view and configure workspaces. A workspace is a space or directory used to organise elements like store or datasets. In GeoServer, a workspace is often used to group similar layers together or to separate 2 layers with the same name but belong to different workspaces.

Add a new workspace

- Select the Workspace button in the menu
- Add a new workspace or choose an existing workspace in the list

Edit a new workspace

- Edit an existing workspace
 - Fill the workspace name
 - Fill the namespace URI (Uniform Resource Identifier)
 - Fill the character set: UTF-8
- Or add a new workspace
 - Select the Add new workspace button
 - Fill the namespace, it is a name describing the project
 - Inform URL: it is the URL associated with this project. It allows a quick and direct access to this workspace.

To finish save the process

Go to store menu to create or choose an existing store (TS8)

TS12. Create a data store

A data store is a connection to a data source, either from a file (e.g. Shape, GeoTIFF...) or Web Services (e.g. WMS, WFS). It is assigned to a workspace; and connects to a data source (e.g. Shape, WFS, WMS or GeoTIFF). The basic process to create a data store in SIMNORAT project is described below.

Edit the data store parameters

This is a non-exhaustive list of parameters to describe in the Edit menu

- **Workspace***: The store is assigned to the selected workspace
- **Data Source Name***: The store name as listed on the view page
- **Description**: A description is then displayed in the administration interface
- **Get Capabilities URL***: This URL returns WebServices parameters and available datasets
- **URL / Shapefile location***: File location on Geoserver set
- **Enabled** (Activated by default): Enable or disable access to the store, along with all layers defined for it.

**Mandatory fields*

Save the store edits.

TS13. Publish a Layer

In GeoServer, the term “layer” refers to the visualisation of a data store. It allows the users, among others things, to define basic information (e.g. title, abstract, projection) but also to set symbology and specific attributes. The basic process to publish a layer in SIMNORAT project is described below.

The diagram illustrates the process of creating or selecting a data store and editing a layer in GeoServer. It is divided into three main sections:

- Create or select a data store (TS7.)**: This section shows a list of data stores (Image, Shape, WFS, WMS) and a selection interface where a layer is chosen from a data store. A green checkmark indicates a successful selection.
- Select a layer in a data store**: This section provides instructions for selecting a data store and a layer. It includes a list of existing stores and a selection interface where a layer is chosen from a data store. A green checkmark indicates a successful selection.
- Edit layer**: This section provides instructions for editing the layer information. It includes a list of tabs to configure the information associated with the layer and a list of parameters to describe the layer.

Create or select a data store (TS7.)

- **Select data store on the left menu**
 - Click on the “Add a new layer” link
- **New layer form**
 - Select a store in the list of existing stores
 - WMS and WFS stores can contain several datasets. Select the one you want to publish in the list displayed
 - , then click on the publish button

Edit layer

4 tabs to configure the information associated with the layer

- **Data**: Describe general information about the layer. This is a non-exhaustive list of parameters to
 - Layer name*: It will be displayed on the layer list
 - Title: Complete name of the layer (by default the layer name)

- Summary : a description of the information
- Bounding box*: URL is filled by default. If not, generate it
- Coordinate Reference System* (CRS): is filled. If not, generate it
- **Publishing:** Defines the layer settings
 - Default style: Choose the style in the drop-down menu (sheet ... Create and publish a Style)
- **Dimension:** Allows user to show elevation or temporality parameters in the get capabilities request (no mandatory field)
- **TileCache:** Improve efficiency by increasing the display speed of layer (no mandatory field)

WFS SHAPE

**Mandatory fields*

Save to finish the publishing process.

Preview the layer

If the layer publication is successful, it is possible to preview the layer in the Layer Preview menu

TS14. Publish a Layer Group

“A layer group is a container in which layers and other layer groups can be organized in a hierarchical structure. A layer group can refer to a single name in “WMS requests” (user manual 2.13). One layer group can be composed of several layers with different bounds and projections.

Add a new layer group

- Select “layer group” button on the menu on the left
- Choose to add a new layer group

Edit the layer group parameters

This is a non-exhaustive list of parameters to describe:

Data

- Name*: The Name of the layer group
- Working space: A layer group within a workspace cannot contain resources from other workspace
- Mode*: The administrator can choose between 4 layer group mode: Single, Named tree, container tree, earth observation tree. Only the single mode has been used in SIMNORAT portal. The layer group is exposed as a single layer with a name, acting as an alias for a list of layers. The layers are still showing up as top level entries in the WMS capabilities document (Geoserver usual manual)

- **Bounds*:** Bounding box is generated from the layers used or from a SRC file. The bounding box generation requires firstly layers to be selected.
- **Layers*:** A layer group can be composed of one or several layers. The order of the layers can be changed for an optimal displaying.

Publishing: Define the layer group setting

TileCache: Improve efficiency by increasing the display speed of the layer group (no mandatory field)

**Mandatory fields*

Save to finish the publishing process

Preview the layer group

If the layer group publication is successful, it is possible to preview the layer

TS15. Create and Publish a Style (SLD)

The integration of hard data (shape, Postgis) and WFS flow requires style management. In GeoServer, styling is accomplished using a markup language called Styled Layer Descriptor, or SLD for short. SLD is an XML-based markup. This page provides an introduction to the capabilities of SLD and how it works within GeoServer. A complete description of SLD concept is available on the Geoserver official Web page (<http://docs.geoserver.org/latest/en/user/styling/sld/introduction.html>)

Create a new SLD file

There are 3 ways to generate a SLD file.

- **Write the SLD Use a text editor that support XML format (e.g. notepad++).** This method requires a well-knowledge of SLD syntax and a lot of time. On the other hand, this is the best way to use the language in its full extent.
- **Generate a SLD file in a GIS software (e.g. QGIS)**
 - Open the file / flow in the GIS Software
 - Change the file / flow style
 - Export the style in SLD

This method doesn't require a well-knowledge of SLD syntax. On the other hand, this feature is not available on all software. In case it is, compatibility gaps can occur.

- **Generate first the SLD file using a GIS software, then customize it using a text editor**

Add a new SLD file in Geoserver

- Select “Styles” on the left menu, then click on “Add a new style”
- Past the SLD in the style editor box or load a SLD file
- Fill at least the name and the store associated with the style in creation
- Click on validate to check syntax errors
- Click on the “apply” button

Associate the SLD file to a layer

One style can be associated with several layers

TS16. Publish a Temporal Layer

In SIMNORAT Map Viewer, it is possible to navigate into time aware datasets. In order to activate this feature on raster datasets (such as maritime traffic), it is needed to create a temporal image mosaic in Geoserver. The whole tutorial is available here: <http://docs.geoserver.org/latest/en/user/services/wms/time.html>

Store data on the server

- Name all the raster files in the same way: name_YYYYMMDD.
- Upload them on the server, in a dedicated folder (called in this sheet DATA_DIR)
- Create in DATA_DIR a file called indexer.properties
- Add the following lines in indexer.properties:

```
TimeAttribute=time
Schema=*the_geom:Polygon,location:String,time:java.util.Date
PropertyCollectors=TimestampFileNameExtractorSPI[timeregex](time)
```

When creating an image mosaic, Geoserver generates a shapefile. This code adds an additional attribute for storing time values

- Create in DATA_DIR a file called timeregex.properties. This file defines how the date is written in the file names
 - Add the following line in timeregex.properties:

```
regex=[0-9]{8} It means that the date is written with 8 digits between 0 and 9
```

Create an Image Mosaic data store

- select “stores” in the left menu, then click on the “Add new store” link
- Select the Image Mosaic Data Store
- Main parameters to fill in:
 - Data source name: name of the image mosaic
 - URL: path to the data folder

Create a layer using the mosaic data store

- select “layers” in the left menu, then click on the “Add a new resource” link
- Select the mosaic data store in the drop-down menu and click on “publish”
- See TS9 – Publish a layer for the main configuration details. The only specificity is on the “Dimensions” tab:
 - Time: tick the “enabled” checkbox
 - Presentation: choose “list”

Check the Geoserver GetCapabilities document

- In a web browser, connect to the Geoserver GetCapabilities address (for SIMNORAT: <http://services.data.simcelt.eu/geoserver/ows?service=wms&version=1.3.0&request=GetCapabilities>)
- If everything is working well, the dataset with the available dates will be shown

```
-<Dimension name="time" default="2016-01-01T00:00:00Z" units="ISO8601">
  2016-01-01T00:00:00.000Z,2016-05-01T00:00:00.000Z,2016-08-01T00:00:00.000Z,2016-11-01T00:00:00.000Z
</Dimension>
```

TS17. Configure a Layer GetFeatureInfo

With Geoserver, clicking on a feature allows to get additional information. By default, it displays the attribute table, but it is also possible to configure it to present information in a different way. The whole tutorial is available here: <http://docs.geoserver.org/latest/en/user/tutorials/GetFeatureInfo/index.html>

Example of "header.ftl"

```
<html>
<head>
  <style type="text/css">
    h2 {
      color: #006494;
    }
  </style>
</head>
<body>
```

Example of "content.ftl"

```
<div>
  <#list features as feature> Loop over the layer
  <ul>
    <li>Country: ${feature.COUNTRY.value}</li>
    </ul>
    <div>
      <#list feature.attributes as attribute>
        <#if attribute.value == "Yes"> Condition on an attribute value
          <div>
            <br />
            ${attribute.name}
          </div>
          Name of an attribute
        </#if>
      </#list>
    </div>
  </#list>
</div>
```

Example of "footer.ftl"

```
</body>
</html>
```

3. Map Viewer

Data and metadata publication on Geonetwork and Geoserver described in the first and second paragraph constitute the primary processes to their publication on SIMNORAT Map Viewer. Then the implementation of metadata and datasets in the data portal illustrator contains 2 processes: Add a layer in the XML file (data sheet 14) and implement a context in the data viewer (data sheet 15).

Figure 15: Map Viewer Processes

TS18. Add a Layer to the Map Viewer

Adding a layer to the map viewer refers to the operation of making a Web Service coming from SIMNORAT Geoserver available with the associated metadata on SDP. This action is realised by manually editing an XML configuration file.

Example of code to insert to simnorat.xml

```
<Layer queryable="true" hidden="false">
  <Server service="OGC:WMS" version="1.3.0">
    <OnlineResource xlink:type="simple" xlink:href="http://wxs-simsp-eu.shom.as8677.net:80/geoserver/ows"/>
  </Server>
  <Name>simnoat:french_maritime_boundaries</Name>
  <Title>Délimitations maritimes (France)</Title>
  <Abstract>abstract content</Abstract>
  <Extension>
    <simsp:Layer>
      <simsp:Category index="3">Boundaries#Maritime Boundaries</simsp:Category>
      <simsp:Downloadable>false</simsp:Downloadable>
      <simsp:Metadatas>
        <simsp:Metadata identifier="BDML_DELMAR.xml">
          <simsp:URL>
            http://services.data.simcelt.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/BDML\_DELMAR.xml
          </simsp:URL>
        </simsp:Metadata>
      </simsp:Metadatas>
      <simsp:Opacity>1.0</simsp:Opacity>
      <simsp:LegendUrl>
        <OnlineResource xlink:href="http://services.data.simnorat.eu/legends/legendes/delmar3.png" xlink:type="simple"/>
      </simsp:LegendUrl>
      <simsp:Originators>
        <simsp:Originator Name="SHOM">
          <simsp:Logo>http://services.data.simnorat.eu/static/logo/SHOM/SHOM.gif</simsp:Logo>
          <simsp:URL>http://www.shom.fr/</simsp:URL>
        </simsp:Originator>
      </simsp:Originators>
    </simsp:Layer>
  </Extension>
</Layer>
```

TS19. Create a Map

Administrators can provide to users custom maps: preconfigured visualisations on a specific spatial extent, with some layers already loaded. Creating a map is done by creating a definition XML file associated with an image, and by adding it in the map catalogue definition file.

Add a layer to the map viewer (3.2.1)

Add a new Map

In the folder `SIMSP_CONTEXT/CONTEXTS/`, create a new document named `context_name.xml`

- Example: `fishing.xml`. It will be the file defining the layers to be viewed on the predefined map.

In `context_name.xml`, add the selected layers

- Add the following lines to `context_name.xml`:
 - Main parameters to configure:
 - `<BoundingBox>`: coordinates to set the initial map extent
 - `<Layer>`: copy a whole `<Layer>` block from the data catalogue file (`simnorat.xml`) for each layer needed on the map

⚠ *The markups are case-sensitive*

Add a screenshot of the map

- Place the image in the folder `SIMSP_CONTEXT/IMAGES`
- The image will be used as an illustration in the Map Catalogue.
- Images must be on the format 350x85

Update the file `SIMSP_CONTEXT/context_catalog.json`

- Add the following lines to the file (just before the last square bracket):
- Items description:
 - title: map name displayed in the map catalogue (in French and English)
 - description: few lines to describe the map (in French and English)
 - image: name of the screenshot
 - file name of the map configuration file

Example of context_name.xml

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?>
<ViewContext xmlns:simps="http://www.simps.eu/context" xmlns:sld="http://www.opengis.net/sld"
xmlns="http://www.opengis.net/context" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-
instance" version="1.1.0" id="simsp_context" xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.opengis.net/context http://wxs-simps-
eu.shom.as8677.net/schema/context/1.1.0/context.xsd http://www.simps.eu/context http://wxs-simps-
eu.shom.as8677.net/schema/simpscontext/1.4.0/context.xsd">
  <General>
    <BoundingBox minx="-2032737.45768780331" miny="5172066.08227026463" maxx="315408.051232811296" maxy="6333908.91220494360"
SRS="EPSG:3857"/>
    <Title>French Maritime Boundaries</Title>
  </General>
  <LayerList>
    <Layer queryable="true" hidden="false">
      <Server service="OGC:WMS" version="1.3.0">
        <OnlineResource xlink:type="simple" xlink:href="http://wxs-simps-eu.shom.as8677.net:80/geoserver/ows"/>
      </Server>
      <Name>simnorat:simnorat_Project_area</Name>
      <Title>SIMNORAT Project Area</Title>
      <Abstract>abstract content</Abstract>
      <Extension>
        <simsp:Layer>
          <simsp:Category index="2">Boundaries#Project Area</simsp:Category>
          <simsp:Downloadable>false</simsp:Downloadable>
          <simsp:Metadatas>
            <simsp:Metadata identifier="LIM.xml">
              <simsp:URL>http://wxs-simps-eu.shom.as8677.net/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/LIM.xml</simsp:URL>
            </simsp:Metadata>
          </simsp:Metadatas>
          <simsp:Opacity>1.0</simsp:Opacity>
          <simsp:Originators>
            <simsp:Originator Name="simnorat">
              <simsp:Logo>http://wxs-simps-eu.shom.as8677.net/static/logo/simnorat/simnorat.png</simsp:Logo>
              <simsp:URL>http://www.simnorat.eu/</simsp:URL>
            </simsp:Originator>
          </simsp:Originators>
        </simsp:Layer>
      </Extension>
    </Layer>
  </LayerList>
```

```
</ViewContext>
```

Contexts_catalog.json – code to add

```
,
{
  "title": {
    "en": "Marine Protected Areas in SIMNORAT Project Area",
    "fr": "Les aires marines protégées dans la zone de projet SMINORAT"
  },
  "description": {
    "en": "This map highlights the availability and representation of data related to marine protected areas in the Northern Atlantic area",
    "fr": "Cette carte illustre la disponibilité et la représentation des données concernant les aires marines protégées dans en Atlantique Nord"
  },
  "image": "mpa.png",
  "file": "mpa.xml"
}
```

Part 3. Challenges

The analysis and data needs and gaps report describes multiples barriers to overcome to increase data use and interoperability in a transboundary context. Then an action plan and architecture have been developed to achieve these objectives.

The quality of data exchange can be enhanced at each step of the data management process:

- The information flow corresponds to the step of collection (importation / exportation), request of data and associated metadata, publication and dissemination
- Understand: The way a dataset is created, associated or not with a metadata can ease the understanding of the dataset by the users.
- Represent means the quality of dataset displaying
- Enhance: Several tools and actions exist to increase the number and the quality of the datasets available for users: Besides the transformation of stored datasets into Web Services, the document describes how the datasets can be developed to access to complex, non-spatial or temporal layers for example.

The sheets below assess how the architecture solves or not the interoperability gaps and what solutions have been or will be developed in the future.

Sheet title: Steps in the data management process

Objective

UNDERSTAND

Ease metadata access

Creation of metadata	Create or complete MD record in accordance with Inspire Directive → Production of metadata by partners : IEO example pending
Give access to metadata catalogue by an URL or by an access button from the portal	Publish MD records using CSW catalogues (add keyword to organise MD and improve research and harvesting)
Ease the metadata research by a search tool (search by keyword or by filter)	Create keywords on published metadata
Impossible to use operator "or" in the research menu	Deepen the filter function of the catalogue
Search possible on a limited number of fields	

Approaches

Provide legends associated with published layers

Generate legends automatically using the Geoserver or the GetLegendGraphic query
No multilingual management of legends available
No manual setting of legends available

Developed actions and examples

Limits

Provide multilingual information

Portal available for users in French and in English version	Produce, translate and disseminate multilingual metadata	Provide metadata in English language as well as native language → Metadata translate by the CEDEX and the Shom: "Maritime Boundaries (France)"
Display data of the portal in English while maintaining the original language (translation of titles and dissemination of data in Web page)	Thematics cannot be translated in the menu "portal data catalogue"	Produce data in English → Multilingual portal: http://data.simwestmed.eu/ et http://data.simporat.eu/
Metadata translation is time-consuming and requires a good knowledge and command of English from producers		→ Production of web pages in English from the attribute data of the layer: Fishing, mariculture, Coastal Marine Ecosystems, Submarine Noise: Zones with probability of accumulation of pressure (Spain)

Actions to develop

Figure 16: Sheet reading guide

INFORMATION FLOW (1)

Organise metadata collection

Deepen the filtering function of Geonetwork harvesting especially in the new version of the Geonetwork	
Impossibility to filter on a field according to several modalities (and/or)	

Assess the compatibility of protocols and standards

Harvest Web services at WMS and WFS formats	
Impossibility to harvest Web services at WCS, SOAP and WMTS formats	
Compatibility issues of tools (implementation of the standard can be different), version issues. For example, some web services of WMS, WFS types do not work.	

Organise metadata dissemination

Publish MD records using CSW catalogues	
---	---

Manage published Web Services instability

Development of an external tool to check the correct functioning of the WebServices and the good setting of the tools → Test the GetMap and GetCapabilities request → Compare Web Services stored in Geoserver and set in the portals → Test whether Web Services set in Geoserver or enable or not.	
	Automatisation of the script execution
	Implementation of an alert system
	Building up programs to check the correct functioning of harvested metadata

INFORMATION FLOW (2)

Organise data dissemination

	Production of Web Services → Production of Web Services by CEDEX and IEO for the needs of the project → Production of Web Services by Shom: <i>Cases studies, SIMNORAT project area, SIMWESTMED project area</i>	
Limitation in the hierarchy of the layers contained in the GetCapabilities. Only the creation of a layer group allows to add a level to the tree		

Publish relevant datasets for the projects and the cases studies

	Populate the data portal demonstrator and enrich the inventory of datasets relevant for the project or the case studies → Create and/or publish new datasets like <i>Cases studies areas, MSFD Atlantic Marine subregions, MSFD Mediterranean Marine subregions</i>	
Difficulties encountered to identify potential users needs		

UNDERSTAND

Ease metadata access

Create or complete MD record in accordance with Inspire Directive → Production of metadata by partners	
Publish MD records using CSW catalogues (add keyword to organise MD and improve research and harvesting)	
Create keywords on published metadata	
Deepen the filter function of the catalogue	
Search possible on a limited number of fields	

Provide legends associated with published layers

Generate legends automatically using the Geoserver or the GetLegendGraphic query
No multilingual management of legends available
No manual setting of legends available

Provide multilingual information

Provide metadata in English language as well as in native language → Metadata translate by the CEDEX and the Shom → Maritime limits and boundaries	
Produce, translate and disseminate multilingual metadata	
Produce data in English → Multilingual portal: http://data.simnorat.eu/ → Production of web page in English from the attribute data of the layer: Fishing, mariculture, Coastal Marine Biocenosis, Submarine Noise: Zones with probability of accumulation of pressure (Spain)	
Thematics cannot be translated in the menu "portal data catalogue"	
Metadata translation is time-consuming and requires a good knowledge and command of English from producers	

REPRESENT

Display transboundary dataset

	Define and produce common symbology to improve understanding and use of datasets → Using INSPIRE specifications to harmonise data : production of " <i>Maritime Boundaries (France)</i> " layer		
	Portrayal management not limited through a graphical interface (SLD language)		
	Establish common rules to define, structure and digitalize the data.		
	Test the use of CSS to manage the portrayal in Geoserver		
	Test more solution to manage the portrayal in a layer group		

ENHANCE

Harness the full potential of the data

	Develop tools to enhance the information → Production of Web pages based on layers attributes <i>Ocean Energy Projects Locations (FTL), Submarine Noise: Zones with probability of accumulation of pressure (FTL)</i> → Production of Web pages based on external database <i>Test Parc Naturels Marins layers (Web) and the Shom has done work to explain the indicators of the MSFD, developed by the FBA in the Carpe Diem project</i>	
 Time-consuming process		
	Think about other tools for managing relational and non-spatial data	
	Deal with more complex relationships between tables	

Manage temporal datasets

	Identify temporal layers in the study areas of the project (AIS)	
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Provide the access of multiple MSP data using thematics

	Creating a map catalogue →The " <i>Maritime boundaries</i> " map shows all the marine boundaries in the SIMNORAT and SIMWESTMED studies areas	
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Communicate about the content of the portal and its features, its evolutions

 Display a dashboard at the start of the portal		
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Share the used tools

	Develop WPS for non spatial and spatial layers	
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Conclusion

The setting up and management of a MSDI demonstrator to share MSP knowledge on the Northern Atlantic proved to be an ideal means to explore data interoperability across a transboundary area. It especially allowed validating the core principles supporting SDP. Among them, the use of web services directly harvested from the data producers' SDI tends to be the most efficient way to collect data from partner infrastructures. It also benefits from an evolving context, thanks to the INSPIRE directive. Nevertheless, when building SDP, many challenges have been encountered, and some solutions to overcome them are proposed.

Some of the difficulties encountered are technical gaps, partly due to interoperability issues. Despite the progress achieved so far, issues can arise from the interaction between different software solutions or protocols. Even when using the same protocols, the differences in protocol versions can generate errors. Other technical challenges lie in being able to take advantage of all the aspects of data, including non-geographical information. This is essential when dealing with time series. A possible solution is to add a web server to the SDI in order to permit more complex GetFeatureInfo requests.

Other challenges fall under organisational matters. The varying availability of web services is still an issue that can prevent access to data for whole areas or categories on SDP. Even when they are available, the durability of web services constitutes a major difficulty. One of the proposed solutions to overcome these difficulties relies on the support to the partner organisations from the resources of European projects. This has been partly applied during SIMNORAT, and could be more intensively exploited in upcoming projects. For the abundance of different data licence policies among data producers, an agreement on a common data licensing at the beginning of a project could allow better use of data from the project partners.

The last kind of challenge encountered is directly linked to data. The most important of these is symbology harmonisation, which is essential when working with data coming from both sides of a boundary. Progressing on this point needs an increased access to Web Feature Services, and a convergence between representation standards on some specific categories.

At a more global scale, SIMNORAT project initiated the cooperation around the Northern Atlantic between stakeholders involved in marine data management in support of Maritime Spatial Planning. The work undertaken by the data and information requirements for MSP component during more than two years can now provide benefits at several levels. Firstly, this baseline information can be used by marine planners in France, Spain and Portugal to start taking into account the transboundary context when elaborating national marine plans. Then, at the European level, interactions have to be set with EMODnet project. As the EMODnet harmonised datasets represented one of the major data sources used in SIMNORAT, the work of inventory done around the Northern Atlantic could be

exploited to complete the coverage of EMODnet, especially concerning the human activities topic.

Finally, the SDI architecture built during the SIMNORAT project will continue to be updated through another European projects dedicated to MSP, SEANSE. This will provide the opportunity to explore interoperability with others European countries, and to complete the data analysis on several European sea basins. It will also give the opportunity to try solving some of the identified challenges by implementing solutions that were imagined during SIMCelt, SIMNORAT and SIMWESTMED projects but could not be experimented.

Annex 1: List of Sources

The datasets selected in the « Analysis on Data Needs and Existing Gaps » report are considered relevant for the MSP because they comply with the requirements defined in this report. The selection criteria relate to the interoperability and the exchange of the data like; “Are they available in Web Services? Is there any associated metadata? Are the licenses open? ...” The selected datasets are listed below and those that are visible in the SIMNORAT portal demonstrator are pointed by the green tick in the table. However, because of incompatibility of standards or protocols and instability related to the web services, some layers may be temporarily unavailable on the SIMNORAT demonstrator portal.

	Category	Sub-Category	Layer Name	Producer	Portal	Metadata
✓	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Communes	OSM	DATA.GOUV.FR	https://www.data.gouv.fr/fr/datasets/decoupage-administratif-communal-francais-issu-d-openstreetmap/
✓	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Départements français	OSM	DATA.GOUV.FR	https://www.data.gouv.fr/fr/datasets/contours-des-departements-francais-issus-d-openstreetmap/
✓	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Régions françaises	Mission etalab	DATA.GOUV.FR	https://www.data.gouv.fr/fr/datasets/contours-des-regions-francaises-sur-openstreetmap/
✓	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Delimitations maritimes	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/BDML_DELMAR.xml
✓	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Communes	IGN (France)	GEOBRETAGNE	http://geobretagne.fr/geonetwork/apps/georchestra/?uuid=b08e6cb1-236c-49b7-88f9-42b500d274d5
✓	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Départements	IGN (France)	GEOBRETAGNE	http://geobretagne.fr/geonetwork/apps/georchestra/?uuid=e16d50d4-746d-44e3-a5e7-5fc000f97665
✓	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Régions	ETALAB	DATA.GOUV.FR	http://geobretagne.fr/geonetwork/apps/georchestra/?uuid=ce22dc5f-2b25-4881-876c-ade7d92aed40
✓	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Concelhos	DGT (Portugal)	Catálogo de Serviços de Dados Geográficos	http://mapas.dgterritorio.pt/geoportal/catalogo.html
✓	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Districtos	DGT (Portugal)	Catálogo de Serviços de Dados Geográficos	http://mapas.dgterritorio.pt/geoportal/catalogo.html
✓	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Freguesias	DGT (Portugal)	Catálogo de Serviços de Dados Geográficos	http://mapas.dgterritorio.pt/geoportal/catalogo.html
✓	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Administrative unit - level 0 /1 /2	Eurogeographics	EEA Discomap	https://www.arcgis.com/sharing/rest/content/items/0b09996863af4b5db78058225bac5d1b/info/metadata/metadata.xml?format=default&output=html
✓	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Limites administrativas	IGN (Spain)	Institut Hydrographico Geoportal	http://www.ign.es/csw-inspire/srv/spa/main.home
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Municipios (polígonos)	IGN (Spain)	Centro de Descargas - Centro Nacional de Informatcion Geografica	
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	European Regional level 1 & 2	Eurogeographics	EEA Discomap	https://www.arcgis.com/sharing/rest/content/items/0b09996863af4b5db78058225bac5d1b/info/metadata/metadata.xml?format=default&output=html
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Comunidades autónomas (polígonos)	IGN (Spain)	Centro de Descargas - Centro Nacional de Informatcion Geografica	
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Provincias (polígonos)	IGN (Spain)	Centro de Descargas - Centro Nacional de Informatcion Geografica	
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Límites autonómicos (líneas)	IGN (Spain)	Centro de Descargas - Centro Nacional de Informatcion Geografica	
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Límites provincias (líneas)	IGN (Spain)	Centro de Descargas - Centro Nacional de Informatcion Geografica	
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Unidades administrativas	IGN (Spain)	Centro de Descargas - Centro Nacional de Informatcion Geografica	http://www.idee.es/csw-inspire-idee/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/spaignwfs_unidades-administrativas_2014
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	European Boundaries	Eurogeographics	EEA Discomap	
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Régions	IGN (France)	GEOBRETAGNE	http://geobretagne.fr/geonetwork/apps/georchestra/?uuid=ce22dc5f-2b25-4881-876c-ade7d92aed40
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	EPCI en Bretagne au 01/01/2017	DREAL Bretagne	GEOBRETAGNE	http://geobretagne.fr/geonetwork/apps/georchestra/?uuid=2298d744-49cb-4fcb-9487-26f916fecdf

	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Communes	IGN (France)	GEOBRETAGNE	http://geobretagne.fr/geonetwork/apps/georchestra/?uuid=b08e6cb1-236c-49b7-88f9-42b500d274d5
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	EPCI	OSM	DATA.GOUV.FR	https://www.data.gouv.fr/fr/datasets/contours-des-epci-2013/
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Límite municipios (líneas)	IGN (Spain)	Centro de Descargas - Centro Nacional de Informacion Geografica	
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Limites terrestres nacionais			http://webgis.dgrm.mam.gov.pt/arcgis/rest/services/Anexo_1_4/Limites_Nacionais/MapServer/0
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Municipalities	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://cepyc22.cedex.es/ArcGIS/services/Shom/MapServer/WMServer
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Comunidades Autonomas CNIG	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://cepyc22.cedex.es/ArcGIS/services/Shom/MapServer/WMServer
	Boundaries	Terrestrial boundaries	Provincias CNIG	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://cepyc22.cedex.es/ArcGIS/services/Shom/MapServer/WMServer
✓	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Lineas de base recta	IHM (Spain)	Geoportal de la Infraestructura de datos espaciales del IHM	ideihm.covam.es/servicios.html
✓	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Mar Territorial	IHM (Spain)	Geoportal de la Infraestructura de datos espaciales del IHM	ideihm.covam.es/servicios.html
✓	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Plataforma continental	IHM (Spain)	Geoportal de la Infraestructura de datos espaciales del IHM	ideihm.covam.es/servicios.html
✓	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Linhas de Base Retas	Hydrographic Institute of Portugal	Geoportal do Instituto Hidrográfico - Portugal	http://mapas.hidrografico.pt/geoserver/AU/ows?service=wms&version=1.3.0&request=GetCapabilities
✓	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Limite Exterior do Mar Territorial	Hydrographic Institute of Portugal	Geoportal do Instituto Hidrográfico - Portugal	http://mapas.hidrografico.pt/geoserver/AU/ows?service=wms&version=1.3.0&request=GetCapabilities
✓	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Délimitation maritimes	Shom (France)	Data.shom.fr	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/BDML_DELMAR.xml
✓	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Polígono da Zona Contígua do Continente	IH	Geoportal do Instituto Hidrográfico - Portugal	http://geoportal.hidrografico.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid=%7B2C7CAF94-684B-4187-BEE8-6EE416407ABF%7D
✓	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Limites da ZEE do Continente	IH	Geoportal do Instituto Hidrográfico - Portugal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/metadados.html?id=209cf0fe-ffb1-4db1-abad-2ee0299d53f4
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Lineas de base recta	INSTITUT CARTOGRAFIC VALENCIA		
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Linha de Base Normal	Instituto Hidrográfico - Portugal		http://mapas.hidrografico.pt/geoserver/AU/ows?service=wms&version=1.3.0&request=GetCapabilities
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Linha de Costa	Instituto Hidrográfico - Portugal	Geoportal do Instituto Hidrográfico - Portugal	http://mapas.hidrografico.pt/geoserver/AU/ows?service=wms&version=1.3.0&request=GetCapabilities
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Linea de costa : DUNAS	Sistema Nacional Informacao De Ambiente	Consejeria De Medio Ambiente Y Ordenacion Del Territorio - Junta De Andalucia	http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_linea_costa_unidades_basicas?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities&
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Contiguous Zones (24nm) V1	VLIZ	MARINEREGIONS.ORG	http://www.marineregions.org/sources.php
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Territorial Sea (12 NM) V1	VLIZ	MARINEREGIONS.ORG	http://www.marineregions.org/sources.php
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Contiguous Zones (24nm) V1	VLIZ	MARINEREGIONS.ORG	http://www.marineregions.org/sources.php
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Exclusive Economic Zones (200 NM) V9	VLIZ	MARINEREGIONS.ORG	http://www.marineregions.org/sources.php
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Maritime boundaries	EEA	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Maritime+Boundaries
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Physical Land /Home made object	Institut Cartografic Valencia	Geoportal de la Infraestructura de datos espaciales del Instituto Hidrográfico de la Marina	http://ideihm.covam.es/geonetwork/srv/spa/csw?REQUEST=GetCapabilities&SERVICE=CSW
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Plataforma continental	Institut Cartografic Valencia	Geoportal de la Infraestructura de datos espaciales del Instituto Hidrográfico de la	

					Marina	
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Mar Territorial	Institut Cartografic Valencia	Geoportal de la Infraestructura de datos espaciales del Instituto Hidrográfico de la Marina	
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Limite de Mar Territorial		IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/TPEA/BaseMapTPEA/MapServer
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Limites maritimos nacionais	Instituto Hidrográfico - Portugal		http://webgis.dgrm.mam.gov.pt/arcgis/rest/services/Anexo_1_4/Limites_Nacionais/MapServer/1
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Linea Base Recta		IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/visorBase/limites_administrativos/MapServer/1
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Linea Zona Contigua		IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/visorBase/limites_administrativos/MapServer/3
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Limite 200 milas - not official		IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/visorBase/limites_administrativos/MapServer/3
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Toponimia do Mar de Portugal	EMEPC	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/emepc/geoserver/Toponimia_do_Mar_de_Portugal/wms
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Limite de salure des eaux		DATA.SHOM.FR	
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Limite de 1 milles		DATA.SHOM.FR	
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Limite de 3 milles		DATA.SHOM.FR	
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Limite de 6 milles			
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Aguas españolas Rada Higuer	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Boundaries	Maritime boundaries	Aguas compartidas Rada Higher	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Pression en surface	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/METEO_R1100_AROME-EURW1S100-MER_20161220.xml
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Vitesse et direction du vent	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/METEO_R1000_ARPEGE-EURAT01-MER_20161212.xml
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Carte sédimentaire mondiale	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/HOM_GEOL_SEDIM_MONDIALE.xml
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Trait de côte Histolitt	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/BDML_TCH.xml
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	EMODnet Digital Bathymetry (DTM)		Emodnet bathymetry Portal	http://www.emodnet-bathymetry.eu/metadata-amp-data/sextant-catalogue-service#/metadata/c7b53704-999d-4721-b1a3-04ec60c87238
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	EMODnet Bathymetry - Mean depth in multi colour		Emodnet bathymetry Portal	https://wxs-simsp-eu.shom2.as8677.net/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/e67f32d1-2e6a-4a6d-97e3-5a6c4704d5fb
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	emodnet bathymetry source references	EMODNET BATHYMETRY	Emodnet bathymetry Portal	http://www.emodnet-bathymetry.eu/v_cdi_v3/browse_step.asp
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Linea de Costa	IEO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/visorBase/limites_administrativos/MapServer/0
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Land water boundary	IHM	Geoportal de la Infraestructura de datos espaciales del Instituto Hidrografico de la Marina	http://ideihm.covam.es/geonetwork/srv/spa/csw?REQUEST=GetCapabilities&SERVICE=CSW

✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Nature du trait de côte	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=517516
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	salinité eau de mer	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/HYDRODYN-SURF_HYCOM3D-SURF_R1000_MANGASC60_20170920.xml
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	température eau de mer	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/HYDRODYN-SURF_HYCOM3D-SURF_R1000_MANGASC60_20170920.xml
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Vitesse et direction du vent	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/METEO_R1000_ARPEGE-EURAT01-MER_20161212.xml
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Raster Marine	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	https://services.mspdata.eu/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/804d20a5-0f3d-4780-9f6b-83b3ee537221
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Carte sédimentaire mondiale	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/HOM_GEOL_SEDIM_MONDIALE.xml
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Sea-floor geology lithology	Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Ressources	Emodnet Geology	http://egdi.geology.cz/csw/?service=CSW&request=GetRecordById&id=1a0d46d6-0f93-4564-9e19-de75480e160b&format=text/html&ElementSetName=brief&lang=en&template=iso2html&lang=en
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Infralittoral Rock Bottom NMD -	IEO	IEO	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Coast typology	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Complexos Recifais ao largo da costa Portuguesa	IPMA		http://maps.ipma.pt/mapserv?map=/var/www/maps/boundaries/biology/recifesgrp_wms.map&language=por&
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Circalittoral Rock Bottom NMD - SIMNORAT	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Carta sedimentológica	IH	IH Geoportal	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Geo-Sítios - Inventário de Sítios com Interesse Geológico	LNEG	LNEG Geoportal	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Altura significativa da onda máxima	LNEG/DGRM	Mar Português Geoportal	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Circalittoral Rock Bottom NMD - SIMNORAT	IEO	IEO	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	World Bathymetry (DLR - EOC)	EOC		
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	World Bathymetry	GEBCO		http://www.gebco.net/data_and_products/gridded_bathymetry_data/gebco_30_second_grid/
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Trait de côte mondiale	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/BDML_TCM_NOAA_HISTOLITT_V2.xml
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Linea de costa : INFRAESTRUCTURAS	CONSEJERIA DE MEDIO AMBIENTE Y ORDENACION DEL TERRITORIO - JUNTA DE ANDALUCIA	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_linea_costa_unidades_basicas?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities&
	Physical, chemical &	Physical	Linea de costa : PLAYAS	CONSEJERIA DE MEDIO AMBIENTE Y ORDENACION DEL TERRITORIO - JUNTA DE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO	http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_linea_costa_unidades_basicas?&service=wms&request

	biological	characteristics		ANDALUCIA	DE AMBIANTE	=getcapabilities&
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Geologie JPG	BRGM	Infoterre BRGM	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=4162
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Corrientes marinas	CONSEJERIA DE MEDIO AMBIENTE Y ORDENACION DEL TERRITORIO - JUNTA DE ANDALUCIA	Visor de información geográfica - Rediam	http://www.ideo.es/csw-inspire-ideo/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/710d9fd2-757c-4dc7-8534-a7feb96cd4cc
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Inventário nacional do património geológico - geosítios marinhos e costeiros	ICNF	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=798194a3-7464-4970-93e8-3498a1bb6a30
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Línea de costa : ACANTILADOS	CONSEJERIA DE MEDIO AMBIENTE Y ORDENACION DEL TERRITORIO - JUNTA DE ANDALUCIA	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_linea_costa_unidades_basicas?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities&
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Línea de costa : ESTUARIOS Y CANOS DE MARISMA	CONSEJERIA DE MEDIO AMBIENTE Y ORDENACION DEL TERRITORIO - JUNTA DE ANDALUCIA	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_linea_costa_unidades_basicas?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities&
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Marnages sur les côtes françaises de La Manche et de l'Atlantique pour le coefficient 20	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/MAREE_COURANTS_MARNAGES_MGA_INF.xml
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Marnages sur les côtes françaises de La Manche et de l'Atlantique pour le coefficient 120	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/MAREE_COURANTS_MARNAGES_MGA_INF.xml
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Hábitat de Interés Comunitario. (2007-2012)	MAPAMA		http://www.mapama.gob.es/ide/metadatos/srv/spa/metadata.show?uuiid=3921abc9-a5bb-434e-828d-501d64b2bd9f
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Isóbatas Maestras	IEO - NSO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/visorBase/Naturaleza_del_Fondo_Marino/MapServer
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Unidades fisiográficas del litoral. Nivel 1	CONSEJERIA DE MEDIO AMBIENTE Y ORDENACION DEL TERRITORIO - JUNTA DE ANDALUCIA		http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_unidades_fisiograficas_litoral?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities&
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Unidades fisiográficas del litoral. Nivel 5	CONSEJERIA DE MEDIO AMBIENTE Y ORDENACION DEL TERRITORIO - JUNTA DE ANDALUCIA		http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_unidades_fisiograficas_litoral?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities&
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Línea de costa : URBANO	CONSEJERIA DE MEDIO AMBIENTE Y ORDENACION DEL TERRITORIO - JUNTA DE ANDALUCIA		http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_linea_costa_unidades_basicas?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities&
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Temperature	GHER - UNIVERSITY OF LIEGE	Seadatanet - Common Data Index (CDI)	http://sdn.oceanbrowser.net/web-vis/?server=http%3A%2F%2Fgher-diva.phys.ulg.ac.be%2Fweb-vis%2Fpython%2Fweb%2Fwms&layers=Mediterranean%20Sea%2FTemperature.19002013.4Danl.nc*Temperature_L2
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Salinity	GHER - UNIVERSITY OF LIEGE	Seadatanet - Common Data Index (CDI)	http://sdn.oceanbrowser.net/web-vis/?server=http%3A%2F%2Fgher-diva.phys.ulg.ac.be%2Fweb-vis%2Fpython%2Fweb%2Fwms&layers=Mediterranean%20Sea%2FTemperature.19002013.4Danl.nc*Temperature_L2
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Sound	IHM	Geoportal de la Infraestructura de datos espaciales del Instituto Hidrográfico de la Marina	ideihm.covam.es/servicios.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Période mer totale	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/WW3_R1000_EURAT01-MFWAM_20161220.xml
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Courant	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/HYCOM2D_MANGASC60_R1000_MANGA_20161212.xml
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Hauteur significative et direction mer totale	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/WW3_R1000_EURAT01-MFWAM_20161220.xml
	Physical, chemical &	Physical characteristics	courants - vitesse maximale	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/MAREE_COURANTS_COURANTS2D.xml

	biological					
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Pression en surface	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/METEO_R1100_AROME-EURW1S100-MER_20161220.xml
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Zone hydrographiques métropole	Sandre	SANDRE	http://www.sandre.eaufrance.fr/atlas/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/8d403ec0-51c7-4372-8b2a-d4a4e24b7365
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Masses d'eau Côtières	Sandre	SANDRE	http://www.sandre.eaufrance.fr/atlas/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/5624dcc4-6611-4f87-8092-443d261b2264
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Batial rock Bottom NMD - SIMNORAT	IEO	IEO	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Hydrographie	IGN (France)		
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Nature de l'estran	UBO - CEREMA		http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=517515
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Laisse de mer			
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Houle	EDF-RD / CEREMA		
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Zonas_climaticas_ROM0391	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Batimetria detalle	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Physical characteristics	Batimetria general	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Echinoturidos Distribution	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Coral Garden Distribution	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Gelidium Distribution	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Lophelia Pertusa Distribution	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Pennatulaceos Distribution	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Non-native points Distribution	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Non-native lineal Distribution	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Physical, chemical &	Biological characteristics	Paracentrotus Lividus Distribution NMD - SIMNORAT	IEO	IEO	

	biological					
	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Distribución de Pennatulaceos DMN - SIMNORAT	IEO	IEO	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Cartographie des habitats coralliens du golf de Gascogne	IFREMER	SEXTANT	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Réseau de suivi des herbiers de Posidonie (TEMPO) - 15m	IFREMER	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportail/sextant#/metadata/8db406fe-5b4f-46be-9e82-d110b15c3afe
	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Réseau de suivi des herbiers de Posidonie (TEMPO) - limite inférieure	IFREMER	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportail/sextant#/metadata/8db406fe-5b4f-46be-9e82-d110b15c3afe
	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Comunidades marinas - Ecocartografía Med-Can	Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación y Medio Ambiente	Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación y Medio Ambiente	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Occurrence of cetaceans	ETC - UMA	SDIMED	http://150.214.47.149:8080/geonetwork/srv/eng/metadata.show?uuid=81fbdcac-06eb-4be4-9738-c1be86912d49
	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Holoturias Distribution NMD - SIMNORAT	IEO	IEO	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Poríferas Distribution NMD - SIMNORAT	IEO	IEO	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Maerl Bottom NMD - SIMNORAT	IEO	IEO	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Mammifères marins (comptage cétacés)	AFB		
	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Requins – raies	APECS		
	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Oiseaux plongeurs	LPO - AFB		
	Physical, chemical & biological	Biological characteristics	Localisation des algues vertes	CEVA		
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	EUSeaMap2 (2016) Broad-Scale Predictive Habitat Map	EMODNET SEABED HABITATS	Emodnet Seabed Habitats Portal	http://gis.ices.dk/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/02a444c8-bd2d-4e15-8e69-806059103760
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	Marine Habitats Point Distribution LBMD	IEO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer/8
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	Marine Habitats Areas Distribution LBMD	IEO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer/15
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	Marine Habitats Facies Distribution LBMD	IEO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer/15
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	EUSeaMap 2016 Habitat Descriptors - Substrate	EMODNET SEABED HABITATS	Emodnet Seabed Habitats Portal	
✓	Physical, chemical &	Types of habitat	EUSeaMap 2016 Habitat Descriptors - Biological zones -	EMODNET SEABED HABITATS	Emodnet Seabed Habitats Portal	

	biological		highly simplified			
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	Broad-Scale Predictive Habitat Map - Confidence	EMODNET SEABED HABITATS	Emodnet Seabed Habitats Portal	http://geonetwork.vliz.be/geonetwork/emodnet/eng/catalog_search#/metadata/90454091-2136-4cb0-a14b-daf09ab20dd0
	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	Modelled Spatial Distributions of Coralligenous Habitats	MEDISEH	Emodnet Seabed Habitats Portal	http://gis.ices.dk/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog_search#/metadata/43c7ac30-04da-479d-b5c1-ba621f0981e4
	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	Modelled Spatial Distributions of Mäerl Habitats	MEDISEH	Emodnet Seabed Habitats Portal	http://gis.ices.dk/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog_search#/metadata/43c7ac30-04da-479d-b5c1-ba621f0981e4
	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	Naturaleza Fondo Marino	IEO	IEO	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	Modelled occurrence probability for Posidonia oceanica meadows across the Mediterranean Sea	IEO	IEO	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	EUSeaMap 2016 Habitat Descriptors - Biological zones - highly simplified	EMODNET SEABED HABITATS	Emodnet Seabed Habitats Portal	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	Zostère MOB (Bassin Marennes Oléron) 2000	IFREMER	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportail/sextant#/metadata/81931b80-02b6-11e0-abec-005056987263
	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	Distribution des herbiers de Zostera noltii et Zostera marina sur l'île de Ré. Etat 1920	IFREMER	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportail/sextant#/metadata/d08aa8d7-a830-43e6-9298-98f39d26ef26
	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	Capacidade de Uso do Solo classificação SROA	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={31B46305-9875-4271-8342-7B9048343D68}
	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	Hábitats de la Directiva Hábitats			http://www.mapama.gob.es/ide/metadatos/srv/spa/metadata.show?uuid=3921abc9-a5bb-434e-828d-501d64b2bd9f
	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	Bancs de maerl en Bretagne		SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/md.format.html?uuid=8df81d30-5a8d-11de-9ad6-000086f6a603&xsl=mdviewer
	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	Fondos marinos	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	8330_Cuevas	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	1170_Arrecifes	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Types of habitat	1110_BancosArena	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Marine Litter Distribution	IEO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer/16
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	indice de sensibilité environnementale du littoral français	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?fileIdentifier=399909ce-8ffd-4938-bb7c-602a3273caa3
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Zonas con potenciales alto y moderado de generacion de ruido submarino	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
✓	Physical, chemical &	Pressures	Acumulacion de presiones que generan ruido submarino	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html

	biological					
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Naturaleza Fondo Marino	IEO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/visorBase/Naturaleza_del_Fondo_Marino/MapServer
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Sites d'immersion des sédiments de dragages portuaires 2005-2015	DEB ;MEEM ; DGITM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?fileIdentifier=8be02bea-2885-4944-8d95-2bfb4de853ab
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Indicateur de pression cummulatif Carpe Diem	AFB		
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Chemical Status	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Zonas sensibles identificadas por polígonos	MAPAMA	Geoportal del Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca Alimentacion medio ambiente (MAPAMA)	http://www.mapama.gob.es/ide/metadatos/index.html?srv=metadata.show&uuid=7ff2d39d-a5dc-4633-974e-9a3cd4335ba6
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Ecological Status - Fitoplancton	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Dumping of dredged material - 2016	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Reg_de emissões e transf_de_poluente__PRTR_	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={B420C865-B513-4B9D-9B72-1D72066C2A71}
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	OSPAR Marine Contaminants - Water	OSPAR COMMISSION	ODIMS (OSPAR DATA PORTAL)	http://odims.ospar.org/layers/geonode:geonode_OSPAR_OSPAR_contaminants_CW_2015/metadata_detail
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Emanações de fluidos submarinos em Portugal (Chaminés Hidrotermais, Pockmarks, Vulcões de Lama)	IPMA		http://maps.ipma.pt/mapserv?map=/var/www/maps/features/geology/offshoremfe_wms.map&SERVICE=WMS&REQUEST=GetCapabilities
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Contaminants in Mussel Distribution NMD - SIMNORAT	IEO	IEO	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Contaminants in Sediment Distribution NMD - SIMNORAT	IEO	IEO	
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Zonas con probabilidad de acumulación de presiones : aloctonas	CEDEX - MAPAMA		http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Zonas con probabilidad de acumulación de presiones : patogenos	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Evlution urbano costa : 1998	CONSEJERIA DE MEDIO AMBIENTE Y ORDENACION DEL TERRITORIO - JUNTA DE ANDALUCIA		http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_tasas_erosion?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Nitrates Directive Surface water Monitoring Stations (2012-2015)	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={8DEDDE65-26C5-4F57-9324-60C99FDDD894}
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Evlution urbano costa : 2001	CONSEJERIA DE MEDIO AMBIENTE Y ORDENACION DEL TERRITORIO - JUNTA DE ANDALUCIA		http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_tasas_erosion?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Evlution urbano costa : 1958	CONSEJERIA DE MEDIO AMBIENTE Y ORDENACION DEL TERRITORIO - JUNTA DE ANDALUCIA		http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_tasas_erosion?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities

Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Evolution urbano costa : 2007	CONSEJERIA DE MEDIO AMBIENTE Y ORDENACION DEL TERRITORIO - JUNTA DE ANDALUCIA		http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_tasas_erosion?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities&
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	indice de sensibilité morpho-sédimentaire du trait de côte du littoral français	MEEM	GÉOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?fileIdentifier=69233543-91ab-4e1a-913f-f26379bdc6d0
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Rede de Monitorização do Estado das Águas Superficiais	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={68544B6A-2BC6-44D9-8F4D-F837690CB689}
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Estação_de_qualidade	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={423FDBCA-141C-4227-882E-9605B5721D4E}
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Estações de monitorização da qualidade das águas superficiais	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={A0529DB8-1963-456C-9D3F-BEB6D780FD1B}
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	OSPAR Marine Contaminants - Biota	OSPAR COMMISSION	ODIMS (OSPAR DATA PORTAL)	http://odims.ospar.org/layers/geonode:geonode_OSPAR_OSPAR_contaminants_CF_2015/metadata_detail
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Rede de Monitorização do Estado Químico das Águas Subterrâneas	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={68544B6A-2BC6-44D9-8F4D-F837690CB689}
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Ponto_de_observação	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={423FDBCA-141C-4227-882E-9605B5721D4E}
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Nitrates Directive Groundwater Monitoring Stations (2012-2015)	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={8DEDDE65-26C5-4F57-9324-60C99FDDD894}
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Rede de Monitorização do Estado Quantitativo das Águas Subterrâneas	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={68544B6A-2BC6-44D9-8F4D-F837690CB689}
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	OSPAR Marine Contaminants - Sediments	OSPAR COMMISSION	ODIMS (OSPAR DATA PORTAL)	http://odims.ospar.org/layers/geonode:geonode_OSPAR_OSPAR_contaminants_CS_2014/metadata_detail
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Inactive Hydrometric Monitoring Station	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={0AC76A9E-5FB9-425A-88DD-0A4F5876A8DE}
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Unidades fisiográficas del litoral alteradas antrópicamente.	CONSEJERIA DE MEDIO AMBIENTE Y ORDENACION DEL TERRITORIO - JUNTA DE ANDALUCIA		http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_unidades_fisiograficas_litoral?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities&
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Mallado de acumulación de presiones - organismos patogenos	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepvc/Demarcaciones.html
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	WFD CW Ecological status - Fitoplancton	CEDEX	CEDEX	
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Environmental Monitoring of Radioactive Substances in Seawater	OSPAR COMMISSION	ODIMS (OSPAR DATA PORTAL)	http://odims.ospar.org/layers/geonode:ospar_seawater_2013_01/metadata_detail
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Environmental Monitoring of Radioactive Substances in Biota	OSPAR COMMISSION	ODIMS (OSPAR DATA PORTAL)	http://odims.ospar.org/layers/geonode:ospar_biota_2013_01/metadata_detail
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Puertos Estado monitoring network	CEDEX	CEDEX	
Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Hydrocarbon surveys	CEDEX	CEDEX	

	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Qualité des zones conchylicoles			
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Zonas con probabilidad de acumulación de presiones: Introducción de basuras marinas desde tierra	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Mallado de acumulación de presiones: Modificación del perfil de fondo y/o enterramiento	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Zonas con probabilidad de acumulación de presiones : del perfil de fondo	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Mallado de acumulación de presiones : Sellado	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Zonas con probabilidad de acumulación de presiones: Sellado	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Zonas con probabilidad de acumulación de presiones: modificación de la sedimentación	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Mallado de acumulación de presiones: Extracción física selectiva	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Zonas con probabilidad de acumulación de presiones: Extracción física selectiva	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Zonas con probabilidad de acumulación de presiones: salinidad	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Mallado de acumulación de presiones: Alteraciones hidrográficas y modificación de la sedimentación	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Mallado de acumulación de presiones: Introducción de basuras marinas desde tierra	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Mallado de acumulación de presiones: Introducción de basuras marinas desde el mar	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Zonas con probabilidad de acumulación de presiones: Contaminación	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Zonas con probabilidad de acumulación de presiones: nutrientes	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Mallado de acumulación de presiones: Salinidad	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Mallado de acumulación de presiones: Contaminación	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
	Physical, chemical & biological	Pressures	Mallado de acumulación de presiones: nutrientes	CEDEX	CEDEX	http://remro.cedex.es/WebCepyc/Demarcaciones.html
✓	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	MSFD Regions and Subregions	EUROPEAN COMMISSION ; EEA ; ETC - UMA	EEA Discomap	http://marine.discomap.eea.europa.eu/arcgis/rest/services/Marine/Marine_regions_subregions/MapServer

✓	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	DCSMM - Sous régions marines (subdivisées)	AFB	EEA DiscomapSEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/md.format.html?uuid=fed29b44-a074-4025-a23c-dfa59942f458&xsl=mdviewer
✓	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	Zones de compétence DIRM	IFREMER	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/csw?SERVICE=CSW&REQUEST=GetCapabilities&VERSION=2.0.2
✓	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	Zones de compétence en mer du préfet de région	IFREMER		
✓	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	Périmètre des SAGE en métropole	Sandre	Sandre	
✓	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	Dominio publico maritimo terrestre	MAPAMA	MAPAMA Acuisvisor	http://www.mapama.gob.es/ide/metadatos/srv/spa/metadatos.show?uuid=6bd4a451-4cc0-4ebb-9687-2119027fd12e
✓	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	Demarcaciones hidrograficas	MAPAMA	MAPAMA Acuisvisor	http://www.mapama.gob.es/ide/metadatos/index.html?srv=metadatos.show&uuid=95b8abce-2083-40b3-bd6b-83a7d8a72307
✓	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	Planos de Ordenamento da Orla Costeira	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SNIAmb	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={A4B78E70-D018-40A7-BC79-6E37F1E9F44C}
✓	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	Demarcaciones marinas	Sandre	Sandre	https://wxs-simsp-eu.shom2.as8677.net/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadatos/6fc5dd46-c608-4223-95e0-25b4cb4815f0
	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	MSFD Marine Districts	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	DCSMM - Sous régions marines	AFB	EEA DiscomapSEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/md.format.html?uuid=fed29b44-a074-4025-a23c-dfa59942f458&xsl=mdviewer
	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	Régions Ospam	OSPAR COMMISSION	OSPAR data and information system	https://odims.ospar.org/geoportal/rest/document?id=%7BEE91EEC8-2E49-4D79-BD91-1365B2266389%7D
	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	Division CIEM/ICES (version SIH)	IFREMER	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/csw?SERVICE=CSW&REQUEST=GetCapabilities&VERSION=2.0.3
	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	Contrats de milieu Métropole	SANDRE	SANDRE	https://wxs-simsp-eu.shom2.as8677.net/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadatos/6fc5dd46-c608-4223-95e0-25b4cb4815f0
	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	Territoires à risques d'érosion	DGPR		
	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	Plans locaux d'urbanisme et cartes communales			
	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	DTA	DREAL		
	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	OGS	DREAL		
	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	Gestion du DPM	DDTM		
	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	SMVM			
	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	Capitanias maritimas	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	Zonas SAR Prisma	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Spatial policy	Spatial policy	PSOEM planta de situação existente		Plano de Situação do Ordenamento do Espaço Marítimo/Mar Português - PSOEM Geoportal	http://webgis.dgrm.mam.gov.pt/arcgis/rest/services/POEM/POEM_Planta_de_S%C3%ADntese_Situa%C3%A7%C3%A3o_Existente/MapServer/info/me
✓	Spatial policy	Land use	Mode d'occupation du sol sur le littoral (LittoMos)	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?fileIdentifier=f63f945a-8295-40b0-90e3-83c1cff208d4
✓	Spatial policy	Land use	Ortho littorale	MEDDE	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?fileIdentifier=99edfd3-c1b2-4879-b58e-6b79a9e5c37c
✓	Spatial policy	Land use	Corine Land Cover	MEEM	Geoportail	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=300875
✓	Spatial policy	Land use	Corine Land Cover 1990 / 2000 / 2006 Spain	IGN (Spain)	Instituto Geografico Nacional	http://centrodedescargas.cnig.es/CentroDescargas/linkMD
✓	Spatial policy	Land use	Corine Land Cover - 2000/2006 - Italy	ISPRA	ISPRA Geoviewer	http://geoportale.isprambiente.it/dettaglio?uuid=ispra_rm%3A20101019%3A110001
	Spatial policy	Land use	Occupation du sol			http://clc.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/geoserver/wms?SERVICE=WMS&REQUEST=GetCapabilities
	Spatial policy	Land use	Coupure d'urbanisation			
	Spatial policy	Land use	Limites latérales de compétences des préfets départementaux/régionaux et maritimes	AFB		http://cartographie.aies-marines.fr/geosource/apps/search/?uuid=79a230c0-a414-46e3-82b7-d90de1a3ae25
	Spatial policy	Land use	Scan littoral	Shom - IGN		
✓	Socio-economic data	Socio-economic data	Employment by Port Authority	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Socio-economic data	Socio-economic data	Demographic Vulnerability 2011	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Socio-economic	Socio-economic	Density of population in	CEDEX	CEDEX	

	data	data	municipalities - 2016			
✓	Socio-economic data	Socio-economic data	Population in municipalities - 2016	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Socio-economic data	Socio-economic data	Indice sensibilité socio-économique du littoral français	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL	
	Socio-economic data	Socio-economic data	Répartition des emplois par type d'activité	SOES		
	Socio-economic data	Socio-economic data	Typologie des grands types de cultures sur le littoral en 2000			
	Socio-economic data	Socio-economic data	Capacité d'hébergement marchande en 2008 (campings et hotel)			
	Socio-economic data	Socio-economic data	Démographie	SOES		
	Socio-economic data	Socio-economic data	Densité de population			
	Socio-economic data	Socio-economic data	Population active – Chômage			
✓	Human activities	Aquaculture	Shellfish production areas	EMODnet Human Activities	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Shellfish+Production
✓	Human activities	Aquaculture	Águas Conquícolas Litorais Portuguesas 2016	IPMA	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/metadados.html?id=f5964449-a188-4c3e-a846-79a1786727de
✓	Human activities	Aquaculture	Zonas de Produção de Moluscos e Bivalves em vigor em Portugal Continental	IPMA	SNIMAR	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/metadados.html?id=e932b735-8546-452b-ac59-a7b8e610854a
✓	Human activities	Aquaculture	Abstrait Instalações de explorações aquícolas	DGRM	SNIMAR	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=78510af6-8d0e-4b50-a831-7e328c46a458
✓	Human activities	Aquaculture	Finfish farming sites	EMODnet Human Activities	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Finfish+Production
✓	Human activities	Aquaculture	Pisciculture existante	IFREMER	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportal/sextant#/metadada/ebcdaa60-ee0e-11dd-87c4-000086f6a603
✓	Human activities	Aquaculture	Cadastre aquacole	DDTM	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadada/95e65d50-88fd-11df-9d72-005056987263
✓	Human activities	Aquaculture	EUROSHELL - Shellfish farmer's organizations	IFREMER	SEXTANT	https://inspire.data.gouv.fr/datasets/f0eb264125e1f4642e12f06f004c4ee033c2947a
✓	Human activities	Aquaculture	Mollusc farming area	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Aquaculture	Fishing vulnerability due to aquaculture	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Aquaculture	Fishing vulnerability due to mollusc farming	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Aquaculture	Aquaculture facilities 2010-2011	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Aquaculture	EMODnet Finfish production	EMODnet Human Activities	EMODnet human activities Portal	https://wxs-simsp-eu.shom2.as8677.net/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadada/fd893ee5-15ca-4035-bf0e-1cac6a8bfe9f
	Human activities	Aquaculture	Abstrait Instalações de explorações aquícolas	DGRM	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=78510af6-8d0e-4b50-a831-7e328c46a458
	Human activities	Aquaculture	Lieux de pêche de laminaires du Finistère	DDTM29	GÉOBRETAGNE	http://geobretagne.fr/geonetwork/apps/georchestra/?uuiid=bee15bd6-0ba8-4042-9eb5-207e1a50cc95
	Human activities	Aquaculture	Potentiel aquacole	IFREMER	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportal/sextant#/metadada/4fa90940-24ed-464e-9318-b7a2e1444db9
	Human activities	Aquaculture	Potentiel pisciculture	IFREMER	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportal/sextant#/metadada/ebcdaa60-ee0e-11dd-87c4-000086f6a603
	Human activities	Aquaculture	EUROSHELL - Shellfish's production areas	IFREMER	SEXTANT	https://inspire.data.gouv.fr/datasets/f0eb264125e1f4642e12f06f004c4ee033c2947a
	Human activities	Aquaculture	Zonas de cria de moluscos 2016 (DMA)		MAPAMA Acuivisor	http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/pesca/temas/acuicultura/zona-produccion-moluscos/
	Human activities	Aquaculture	Zonas de cria de moluscos 2016 (DMA)		MAPAMA Acuivisor	http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/pesca/temas/acuicultura/zona-produccion-moluscos/
	Human activities	Aquaculture	Zones de production conchylicoles	Office International de l'eau	Atlas des zones de production et de réparation de coquillages	http://www.atlas-sanitaire-coquillages.fr/statuts

✓	Human activities	Fishing	Les cantonnements de pêche dans les eaux françaises	AFB	AFB Cartomer	http://cartographie.aires-marines.fr/geosource/apps/search/?uuiid=17197870-0222-4f80-9961-0685dc7d06be
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Données VMS en 2013-2014		SEXTANT	
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Fishing Effort Bottom Trawl Doors Distribution NMD	IEO	IEO	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Fishing Effort Bottom Trawl Couples Distribution NMD	IEO	IEO	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Fishing Effort Bottom Troll Distribution NMD	IEO	IEO	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Fishing Effort Bottom Longline Distribution NMD	IEO	IEO	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Fishing Effort Traps Distribution NMD	IEO	IEO	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Fishing Effort Bottom Gillnets Distribution NMD	IEO	IEO	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Fishing Effort Hand lines Distribution NMD	IEO	IEO	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Fishing Effort Live Bait Distribution NMD	IEO	IEO	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Subceptible Fishes Species	IEO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer/16
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Fishing Effort Bottom Trawl Distribution	IEO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer/25
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Fishing Effort Purse-Seine	IEO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer/20
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Fishing Effort Gillnets Distribution	IEO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer/19
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Fishing Effort Bottom Longline Distribution	IEO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer/24
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Fishing Effort Traps Distribution	IEO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer/22
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Fishing Effort Top Longline Distribution	IEO		http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/MSFD/IEO_MSFD_DMLB/MapServer/24
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Geographical subareas (GSAs)	GFCM		http://www.fao.org/gfcm/data/map-geographical-subareas/en/
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Fish markets	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Total number of vessels 2016	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Number of vessels GNS 2016	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Number of vessels LLD 2016	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Number of vessels LLS 2016	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Number of vessels PS 2016	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Number of vessels OTB 2016	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Fishing	Number of vessels PTB 2016	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Human activities	Fishing	Portaria n.º 114/2014: Proteção da VME	Legislation and DGRM	PSOEM Geoportal	http://webgis.dgrm.mm.gov.pt/arcgis/rest/services/PSOEM/Protecao_da_VME/MapServer
	Human activities	Fishing	Relevância da pesca local	Relevância da pesca local	DGRM	http://webgis.dgrm.mam.gov.pt/arcgis/rest/services/PSOEM_GEOPORTAL/relevancia_pesca_local/MapServer
	Human activities	Fishing	Zones d'autorisation de pêche dans les eaux françaises par les navires étrangers (version SIH)	AFB	SEXTANT	http://www.ifremer.fr/services/wms/sih_referentiels?SERVICE=WMS&REQUEST=GetCapabilities
	Human activities	Fishing	Zones de pêche et activité en mer	MEDOBS	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/db439bee-590a-431d-9f2d-ecd8080b7019
	Human activities	Fishing	Confraries de pescadors	Govern Illes Balears	INFRAESTRUCTURA DE DADES	

				ESPACIALS DE LES ILLES BALEARS	
	Human activities	Fishing	Caladeros	IEO	IEO Portal http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/visorBase/Usos_del_medio/MapServer/0
	Human activities	Fishing	Criées	IFREMER	SEXTANT http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportail/sextant#/metadata/d6d54f74-c463-43e4-99f3-d5ba43c1012e
	Human activities	Fishing	Lignes interdiction de chalutage du Finistère	DDTM29	GÉOBRETAGNE http://geobretagne.fr/geonetwork/apps/georchestra/?uuiid=6d379b7d-27c0-4a4b-8f9e-5fd4f209aa37
	Human activities	Fishing	Casiers à crustacés	CRPMEM Bretagne	SEXTANT http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportail/sextant#/metadata/f924c0a4-86f9-47a0-853c-2ff0851dc567
	Human activities	Fishing	Brest métropole : Zones de pêche en Rade de Brest	BREST MÉTROPOLE	GÉOBRETAGNE http://geobretagne.fr/geonetwork/apps/georchestra/?uuiid=ECO_PEC_ZonesPeche
	Human activities	Fishing	Dragues à la Praire	CRPMEM Bretagne	SEXTANT http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog_search#/metadata/3974dc2b-3090-4fe0-83c3-0b72164e6cfe
	Human activities	Fishing	Casiers à Bulot	CRPMEM Bretagne	SEXTANT http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportail/sextant#/metadata/87186aa6-6b65-4f95-9c51-96e0fc1cb4a1
	Human activities	Fishing	Chalut de fond à la crevette	CRPMEM Bretagne	SEXTANT
	Human activities	Fishing	Unités d'exploitation et de gestion (UEG)	IFREMER	SEXTANT
	Human activities	Fishing	GT - Gross tonnage 2016	CEDEX	CEDEX
	Human activities	Fishing	Réglementation pêche (arrêtés)	DPMA – DDTM - DIRM	
	Human activities	Fishing	Zones fonctionnelles halieutiques (bar, merlan, plie, sole)	IFREMER	
	Human activities	Fishing	Pêcheries	DDTM	
	Human activities	Fishing	Zones de production de coquillages	DDTM	
	Human activities	Fishing	Flottes de pêche	CRPMEM	
	Human activities	Fishing	Statistiques de pêche : tonnage à la débarque, emploi	DDTM - CRPMEM	
	Human activities	Fishing	Pêche récréative	DPMA	
	Human activities	Fishing	Valor primera venta por Autoridad Portuaria	CEDEX	CEDEX
✓	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	Ocean energy facilities	AZTI-TECNALIA	EMODnet human activities Portal http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Project+Locations
✓	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	Ocean energy Projects location	AZTI-TECNALIA	EMODnet human activities Portal http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Project+Locations
✓	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	EMODnet Wind Farms	CETMAR	EMODnet human activities Portal http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Wind+Farms+%28Points%29
✓	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	Ocean energy facilities : Project location	AZTI-TECNALIA	EMODnet human activities Portal http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Project+Locations
✓	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	Eolien flottant : appel à projet 2015 (point)	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?fileIdentifier=24c10127-6c52-411d-9b2a-8399cbbff06b
✓	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	Eolien flottant : appel à projet 2015 (polygones)	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?fileIdentifier=a00c44c2-4965-48a4-9c6e-2cd586bc7e80
✓	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	Eolien flottant : Gisement technique	DGES ; MEEM	GEOLITTORAL http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?fileIdentifier=88ce8c03-55ab-4693-a1cf-dd0a8bbfb543
✓	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	Eolien posé : Gisement technique	MEEM ; DGES	GEOLITTORAL http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?fileIdentifier=091faeb-ed41-4947-a32f-2c42d142169e
✓	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	Gisement technique pour le développement de l'énergie houlomotrice	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?fileIdentifier=8ed5490d-255c-44ec-ac57-abe44fed1f99
✓	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	Wind zones	CEDEX	CEDEX no metadata
	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	Áreas existentes e áreas potenciais	DGRM	PSOEM Geoportal http://webgis.dgrm.mm.gov.pt/arcgis/rest/services/PSOEM_GEOPORTAL/PSOEM_Eolicas_geoportal/MapServer/0
	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	AMI hydrolien : résultat concertation 2013	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?fileIdentifier=24c10127-6c52-411d-9b2a-8399cbbff06b
	Human activities	Marine Renewable	AMI hydrolien : zones propices à	DGES - MEDDE	GÉOLITTORAL http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=367657

		Energies	l'implantation des fermes pilotes			
	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	OSPAR Offshore Renewable Energy developments	OSPAR COMMISSION	ODIMS (OSPAR DATA PORTAL)	http://odims.ospar.org/layers/geonode:ospar_offshore_renewables_2014_01/metadata_detail
	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	Energies Marines Renouvelables	IFREMER		
	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	Eolien posé : appel d'offre 2011	MEEM	GÉOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?fileIdentifier=79d4e05a-755f-4362-97a6-a771e67d659f
	Human activities	Marine Renewable Energies	BIMEP	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Installations and infrastructure	Arrecifes Artificiales Zonas	IEO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/visorBase/Usos_del_medio/MapServer/2
✓	Human activities	Installations and infrastructure	Arrecifes Artificiales Poligonos	IEO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/visorBase/Usos_del_medio/MapServer/2
✓	Human activities	Installations and infrastructure	Ouvrages et aménagements littoraux	CEREMA ; MEEM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=564691
✓	Human activities	Installations and infrastructure	Wrap Areas	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Installations and infrastructure	Desalination plants	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Installations and infrastructure	Natural Gaz storage platform	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Human activities	Installations and infrastructure	Complexos recifais - Áreas existentes e áreas potenciais	DGRM	PSOEM Geoportal	
	Human activities	Installations and infrastructure	Mouillages ou abris	IFREMER	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/d2ac9538-ba63-46d3-9a36-8e1d1e046b26
	Human activities	Installations and infrastructure	Titulos de Utilização Privativa do Espaço Marítimo para Infraestruturas e equipamentos	DGRM	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/metadados.html?id=0d4297c9-4a58-4f8e-bcd2-46a7c3746b17
	Human activities	Installations and infrastructure	Bridge	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Human activities	Installations and infrastructure	Waste water treatment plants	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Human activities	Installations and infrastructure	Aménagements (cale, gabions, épis...)	DDTM		
	Human activities	Installations and infrastructure	Stations de traitement des eaux usées	MEDDE		http://www.sandre.eaufrance.fr/atlas/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/ebef2115-bee5-40bb-b5cc-4593d82ba334
	Human activities	Installations and infrastructure	Stations de traitement des eaux usées (rejets)	MEDDE		http://www.sandre.eaufrance.fr/atlas/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/ebef2115-bee5-40bb-b5cc-4593d82ba334
	Human activities	Installations and infrastructure	Périmères de protection des centrales nucléaires	MTES		
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	Localisation des CROSS	CROSS	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/1a6fbfa4-24a2-4eae-b017-962145ce442d
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	Nombre estimé de cargos sur l'année 2016	MEEM ; DGITM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=556519
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	EMODnet Lighthouses	AMATEUR RADIO LIGHTHOUSE SOCIETY	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Lighthouses
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	light	IHM	Geoportal de la Infraestructura de datos espaciales del Instituto Hidrografico de la Marina	ideihm.covam.es/servicios.html
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	Nombre estimé de navires de ' Class B' sur l'année 2016	MEEM ; DGITM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=556519
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	Nombre estimé de navires de ' passagers' sur l'année 2016	MEEM ; DGITM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=556519
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	Nombre estimé de navires de pêche sur l'année 2016	MEEM ; DGITM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=556519

✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	Nombre estimé de navires toutes catégories sur l'année 2016	MEEM ; DGITM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=556519
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	Nombre estimé de tankers sur l'année 2016	MEEM ; DGITM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=556519
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	Nombre estimé de yachts sur l'année 2016	MEEM ; DGITM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=556519
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	Chenaux d'accès aux ports	CEREMA	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/f3255cda-e0e0-476c-b7ca-41cf9ae2fd11
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	Motorways of the seas	EUROPEAN COMMISSION		http://data.adriplan.eu/layers/geonode%3Amotorways_seas_4326#more
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	Alerts and accidents between 2008 and 2014	ETC - UMA	SDIMED	http://150.214.47.149:8080/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/c40ba87f-dee2-4a67-af5a-02f5372be1bd
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	Banned Anchorages Area	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	Traffic separation schema	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	Anchoring areas	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Maritime transport	AIS signal in a month	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Human activities	Maritime transport	Nautical chart	IHM	Geoportal de la Infraestructura de datos espaciales del Instituto Hidrográfico de la Marina	ideihm.covam.es/servicios.html
	Human activities	Maritime transport	Liaisons maritimes du finistère	DDTM29	GÉOBRETAGNE	http://geobretagne.fr/geonetwork/apps/georchestra/?uuiid=a4a4770d-aafe-4b60-9ac7-62473bb51647
	Human activities	Maritime transport	Zone de transbordement	CRPMEM Bretagne	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/95a4dc22-08ab-44da-b86b-a44add4f4432
	Human activities	Maritime transport	Alerts and accidents between 2008 and 2014	CRPMEM Bretagne	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/95a4dc22-08ab-44da-b86b-a44add4f4432
	Human activities	Maritime transport	Données AIS 2016	IFREMER	SEXTANT	
	Human activities	Maritime transport	Trafic de marchandise (volume)	SOES		
	Human activities	Maritime transport	Dispositif de Séparation du Trafic	CEDRE	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/md.format.html?uuiid=043a0ae0-8973-11dd-a9f2-000086f6a62e&xsl=mdviewer
	Human activities	Maritime transport	Mouillage groupé / individuel	DDTM		
	Human activities	Maritime transport	Établissements de signalisation maritime (ESM): phares, balises, feux, bouées ...	Shom		
	Human activities	Maritime transport	Autoroutes des mers			
✓	Human activities	Ports	EMODnet Main Ports (Passagers Traffic)	COGAEUROFISH	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Main+Ports
✓	Human activities	Ports	EMODnet Main Ports (Good Traffic)	COGAEUROFISH	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Main+Ports
✓	Human activities	Ports	EMODnet Main Ports (Vessel Traffic)	COGAEUROFISH	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Main+Ports
✓	Human activities	Ports	EMODnet Main Ports	COGAEUROFISH	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Main+Ports
✓	Human activities	Ports	Ports (version SIH)	IFREMER	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportal/sextant#/metadata/998f4c00-a7fa-11dc-bb52-000086f6a62e
✓	Human activities	Ports	Total goods	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Ports	State Owned Ports	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Human activities	Ports	Localisation des ports et bassins par typologie		SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/ea052986-1dd7-4709-98ce-b211c81daee1
	Human activities	Ports	Ports de Bretagne	RÉGION BRETAGNE	GÉOBRETAGNE	http://geobretagne.fr/geonetwork/apps/georchestra/?uuiid=c55c4fba-6a37-48ea-8754-a1bf770a684b
	Human activities	Ports	Public port domain	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Human activities	Ports	Other ports	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Human activities	Ports	Profundidad bocana	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Human activities	Ports	Trafico de contenedores	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Human activities	Ports	Mercancias Graneles Solidos	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Human activities	Ports	Mercancias Graneles Liquidos	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Nature and species	EMODnet Natura 2000 sites	COGEA	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE; EMODnet human	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Natura+2000

		conservation			activities Portal	
✓	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	EMODnet Nationally Designated Areas	COGEA	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE; EMODnet human activities Portal	http://77.246.172.208/geoserver/emodnet/wfs?VERSION=1.1.0&
✓	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Designated marine protected areas (points)	AFB	MAIA WEB GIS	http://cartographie.aires-marines.fr/geosource/apps/search/?uuiid=ospar_mpa_2014_01
✓	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Sites Ramsar - métropole	MNHN	Inventaire National du Patrimoine Naturel	http://metadata.carmencarto.fr/geosource/119/fre/find?uuiid=1DB87106-328F-4718-90B1-E0B3FE875B0C
✓	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Terrains du conservatoire du littoral - métropole	MNHN	Inventaire National du Patrimoine Naturel	http://metadata.carmencarto.fr/geosource/119/fre/find?uuiid=3e79098c-6875-4442-a3e0-d1465471bddf
✓	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Zones humides d'importance majeure	ONZH	RPDZH	http://www.geosource.reseau-zones-humides.org/geosource/srv/fre/catalog_search#/metadata/c2110625-8942-463b-8cbd-c97578858592
✓	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Ecologically or Biologically Significant Marine Areas	ICNF	PSOEM	http://si.icnf.pt/geoserver/POEM/ebsa/wms?versio=1.3.0&SERVICE=WMS&REQUEST=GetCapabilities
✓	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Zonamento Reservas da Biosfera do POEM	ICNF	PSOEM	http://si.icnf.pt/geoserver/POEM/biosfera_zonamento_poem/wms?versio=1.3.0&SERVICE=WMS&REQUEST=GetCapabilities
✓	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Parcs naturels marins	AFB		
✓	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Les Aires Marines Protégées françaises	AFB		
✓	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Sites de suivi des macrodéchets - Parc naturel marin d'Iroise	AFB		
✓	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Sites de suivi des contaminants - Parc naturel marin d'Iroise	AFB		
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Designated marine protected areas (polygons)	AFB	MAIA WEB GIS	http://cartographie.aires-marines.fr/geosource/apps/search/?uuiid=ospar_mpa_2014_01
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Limites das Zonas de Proteção Especial marinhas, estuarinas e costeiras (ZPE)	ICNF	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=88b6a049-695d-44b7-a3c2-b022d986585f
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Limites dos Sítios de Importância Comunitária - RN2000/SIC	ICNF	SNIG and SNIMAR http://geocatalogo.icnf.pt/	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=378877ae-32bb-4218-b276-ef9f85208cc0
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	AMP Propostas	DGRM	PSOEM Geoportal	
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Áreas marinhas protegidas	DGRM	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/metadados.html?id=86b2f071-7955-4f39-8539-96c1ac9f8e15
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Áreas protegidas marinhas e costeiras	ICNF	SNIG and SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=23cf7b19-22dd-4bb2-8522-5607117814e6
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Aire de protection du biotope	AFB	AFB Cartomer	http://cartographie.aires-marines.fr/geosource/apps/search/?uuiid=5ec5bc51-3533-4648-a836-c72132199492
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Réserve naturelle	AFB	AFB Cartomer	http://cartographie.aires-marines.fr/geosource/apps/search/?uuiid=42f12513-a875-4172-8dfb-aca8cde12411
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Inventario Espanol de Zonas Humedas (IEZH_ES)	MAPAMA	Geoportal del Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca Alimentacion medio ambiente (MAPAMA)	http://www.mapama.gob.es/ide/metadatos/index.html?srv=metadata.show&uuiid=98a15f5f-666d-45d9-a972-ff3a73f8479b
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Zone spéciale de conservation	AFB	AFB Cartomer	http://cartographie.aires-marines.fr/geosource/apps/search/?uuiid=7624364c-e548-4298-af61-e318ef6ae055
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Site d'importance communautaire	AFB	AFB Cartomer	http://cartographie.aires-marines.fr/geosource/apps/search/?uuiid=7624364c-e548-4298-af61-e318ef6ae055
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	_Zonas_Húmidas__Sítios_RAMSA R_	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuiid={31B46305-9875-4271-8342-7B9048343D68}
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Zone de protection spéciale	AFB	AFB Cartomer	http://cartographie.aires-marines.fr/geosource/apps/search/?uuiid=f7e485d5-bd02-496c-a749-5af9505271a5
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Parcs naturels marins - métropole	MNHN	Inventaire National du Patrimoine Naturel	http://metadata.carmencarto.fr/geosource/119/fre/metadata.show?uuiid=193b1776-420f-44eb-86c8-4144fda4b0ba

	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	ZNIEFF 2 mer	MNHN	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE ; Inventaire National du Patrimoine Naturel	
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Humedales RAMSAR	MAPAMA	MAPAMA Acuisvisor	http://www.mapama.gob.es/ide/metadatos/srv/spa/metadatos.show?uuid=fb326c11-18d4-4ee1-aa23-a40cb90cf8d8
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Planos de Ordenamento da Orla Costeira (POOC)	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/metadados.html?id=C70CF6CB-0554-4A61-B215-A79F73B9E267
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Espaces remarquables	CEREMA	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/66d5d365-44a7-4855-ae8-7deb79bf645
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	PSRN2000 - Valores naturais da diretiva aves		SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=34a234e8-1eac-4aa5-9771-b486d49ea4f5
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Réserves nationales de chasse et de faune sauvage	MNHN	CARMEN/GeoIDE	http://metadata.carmencarto.fr/geosource/119/fr/find?uuid=7691AB04-9A22-445A-938D-BD7F11ABE9A2
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Limites das Áreas Protegidas marinhas, estuarinas e costeiras (AP)	ICNF	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=23cf7b19-22dd-4bb2-8522-5607117814e6
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	PSRN2000 - Orientações de gestão - . Condicionar a denagem	ICNF	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=55d3fa0f-ad02-4806-96df-c577ac59900f
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	PSRN2000 - Orientações de gestão - 24. Recuperar zonas húmidas	ICNF	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/metadados.html?id=1871f179-401d-4f78-91dd-6621ddbc74e8
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Plantas de síntese dos planos de ordenamento das Áreas Protegidas marinhas e costeiras - WFS	ICNF	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/metadados.html?id=8cdc3d8e-0cb1-46e2-a424-3a3cc6e7aabc
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	PSRN2000 - Orientações de gestão - . Recuperar zonas húmidas	ICNF	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=1871f179-401d-4f78-91dd-6621ddbc74e8
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Áreas importantes para as aves marinhas e costeiras (IBAs)	ICNF	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=abf8225f-808d-42e4-a17f-5094e38f51fc
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	PSRN2000 - Orientações de gestão - . Condicionar pesca	ICNF	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=336fbcff-ae9-4173-bdd7-053194f88519
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Limites das Zonas de Proteção Especial marinhas, estuarinas e costeiras (ZPE)	ICNF	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=88b6a049-695d-44b7-a3c2-b022d986585f
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Limites dos Sítios de Importância Comunitária marinhos, estuarinos e costeiros (SIC)	ICNF	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=378877ae-32bb-4218-b276-ef9f85208cc0
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	PSRN2000 - Orientações de gestão - . Tomar medidas que impeçam conversão de sapais	ICNF	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=647de264-6630-4efe-9c28-35dad374869
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	PSRN2000 - Orientações de gestão - . Manter / recuperar salinas	ICNF	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=76b070f7-1baa-4b88-91f2-03c25f082f28
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Limites das Zonas de Proteção Especial marinhas, estuarinas e costeiras	ICNF	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=17306f818c0944cbbc16fc63d46b2693
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Corridors biologiques mammifères marins	DREAL		
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Biens du patrimoine mondial de l'UNESCO	DREAL		http://metadata.carmencarto.fr/geosource/119/fr/find?uuid=9a0acb6e-17e2-4e0b-be6c-fa53c8384b8a
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Sanctuaires Pelagos	DREAL		
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Sites classés sous forme de polygones	DREAL		http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/da014df3-cb08-4cf9-be9f-aea772219a9c
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Sites inscrits sous forme de polygones	DREAL		http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/54592e42-f3ef-4b38-8844-d16a6ea29ef2
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Atlas des paysages	DREAL		

Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Reservas de la Biosfera	MAPAMA	Geoportal del Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca Alimentacion medio ambiente (MAPAMA)	http://www.mapama.gob.es/ide/metadatos/index.html?srv=metadata.show&uuid=5353db93-fcb3-4be3-a4ff-39bbf25429ce
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Red Natura 2000	MAPAMA	Geoportal del Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca Alimentacion medio ambiente (MAPAMA)	http://www.mapama.gob.es/ide/metadatos/index.html?srv=metadata.show&uuid=0d427e21-be52-4723-b78e-8b00a43319cb
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Areas Importantes para las Aves en Espana (IBAS)	MAPAMA	Geoportal del Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca Alimentacion medio ambiente (MAPAMA)	http://www.mapama.gob.es/ide/metadatos/index.html?srv=metadata.show&uuid=9ca4f461-102a-4bc5-a7ed-7925153e69b4
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Lugar de Importancia Comunitaria. LIC	MAPAMA	Geoportal del Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca Alimentacion medio ambiente (MAPAMA)	http://www.mapama.gob.es/ide/metadatos/index.html?srv=metadata.show&uuid=aae202fb-ffd6-4acb-8c1b-3280578f7067
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Inventario Espanol Areas Protegidas	MAPAMA	Geoportal del Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca Alimentacion medio ambiente (MAPAMA)	http://www.mapama.gob.es/ide/metadatos/index.html?srv=metadata.show&uuid=a8f1d828-c073-443e-8500-d2d3d6a021df
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Red OSPAR de áreas marinas protegidas	MAPAMA Acuivisor	Geoportal del Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca Alimentacion medio ambiente (MAPAMA)	http://www.mapama.gob.es/ide/metadatos/srv/spa/metadata.show?uuid=d1d35488-2c38-4288-a463-359165bff122
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Zonas especialmente Protegidas de Importancia para el Mediterraneo (ZEPIM_ES)	MAPAMA	Geoportal del Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca Alimentacion medio ambiente (MAPAMA)	http://www.mapama.gob.es/ide/metadatos/index.html?srv=metadata.show&uuid=cb550555-548b-450f-bee1-4435a4c40b6c
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Espacios Naturales Protegidos	MAPAMA	Geoportal del Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca Alimentacion medio ambiente (MAPAMA)	
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Red de Areas Marine Protegidas de Espana (RAMPE)	MAPAMA	Geoportal del Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca Alimentacion medio ambiente (MAPAMA)	http://www.mapama.gob.es/ide/metadatos/index.html?srv=metadata.show&uuid=7672013f-69a7-49c9-b7f4-9aaaa525c6d3
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Zone importante pour la Conservation des Oiseaux	MNHN	Inventaire National du Patrimoine Naturel	http://metadata.carmencarto.fr/geosource/119/fr/find?uuid=51656df6-5ced-4d57-9c0f-636441ee8c2b
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Sites d'importance communautaire désignés par la France	MNHN	Inventaire National du Patrimoine Naturel	http://metadata.carmencarto.fr/geosource/119/fr/find?uuid=EC389F13-669A-4611-942C-C187E7F523E2#
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Arrêtés de protection biotopes - métropole	MNHN	Inventaire National du Patrimoine Naturel	http://metadata.carmencarto.fr/geosource/119/fr/find?uuid=e9fa856d-cb94-42c0-9822-8bea799199ac#
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Sites du conservatoire des espaces naturels	MNHN	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog_search#/metadata/8dcd4319-3834-499b-b866-cade3efb5cbf
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Réserves de biosphère - métropole	MNHN	Inventaire National du Patrimoine Naturel	http://metadata.carmencarto.fr/geosource/119/fr/find?uuid=A4416114-D220-49A5-A1F8-B6C4C18043BC#
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Parcs nationaux - métropole	MNHN	Inventaire National du Patrimoine Naturel	http://metadata.carmencarto.fr/geosource/119/fr/metadata.show?uuid=195455A0-351A-4A11-8CC2-CD6ED1471326
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Espaces naturels sensibles	MNHN	CARMEN/GeoIDE	http://metadata.carmencarto.fr/geosource/119/fr/find?uuid=8096899c-c82c-4ed7-9638-5eb599b20071
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Projet de parc naturel marin	MNHN		
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	NATURA 2000 – Directive Habitats (SIC et ZSC)	MNHN		
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	NATURA 2000 – Directive Oiseaux (ZPS)	MNHN		
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Inventaire zones humides			
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Áreas de Cons. da Natureza Biótopos CORINE_	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={31B46305-9875-4271-8342-7B9048343D68}
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	mpatlas_2017_01	MARINE CONSERVATION INSTITUTE	MPATLAS	
Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Zonamento Reservas da Biosfera do POEM	ICNF		http://si.icnf.pt/geoserver/POEM/biosfera_zonamento_poem/wms?versio=1.3.0&SERVICE=WMS&REQUEST=GetCapabilities

	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Reservas Marinas Usos	IEO	IEO Portal	http://barretosm.md.ieo.es/arcgis/rest/services/visorBase/Naturaleza_del_Fondo_Marino/MapServer
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Áreas Marinhas Protegidas Oceânicas Nacionais	SNIMAR Geoportal		
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Complexos Recifais ao largo da costa Portuguesa	IPMA		http://maps.ipma.pt/mapserv?map=/var/www/maps/boundaries/biology/recifesgrp_wms.map&SERVICE=WMS&REQUEST=GetCapabilities
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Corridors biologiques mammifères marins	CELRL		
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	Corridors biologiques avifaune			
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	GSI N2000 au large Récifs	DEB		
	Human activities	Nature and species conservation	GSI N2000 au large Oiseaux et mammifères marins	DEB		
✓	Human activities	Military	Dumped munitions - polygon	CETMAR	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Dumped+Munitions+%28Polygons%29
✓	Human activities	Military	Localisation des sémaphores	CEREMA ; Préfectures maritimes	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/2471ba17-bc61-4308-9e99-1d0677d5d8fe
✓	Human activities	Military	Zone de tir	CEREMA	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportail/sextant#/metadata/606faadf-5538-496f-8894-2c37dea86ba8
✓	Human activities	Military	Military zones	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Military	Munition disposal sites	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Military	Zone de dépose de munitions	CEREMA	SEXTANT	
	Human activities	Military	Áreas de exercícos militares	AMN/IH	PSOEM Geoportal	
	Human activities	Military	Zone de tirs d'essais	CEREMA	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportail/sextant#/metadata/f5fd6fef-433e-46d7-8a98-8e9a4c3756d8
	Human activities	Military	Zones de protection sémaphore	Préfectures maritimes		https://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/a7011ef3-6e33-431c-b5ea-a669c635275a
	Human activities	Military	Radars aériens	ZAD nord et sud		http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/94ae175b-a4c9-4c8d-916d-6e5c70aefddd
	Human activities	Military	Zones de protection (défense aérienne)	ZAD nord et sud		https://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/da6503e9-7276-42c9-873c-3c7289a56ece
	Human activities	Military	Zone de plageage	IFREMER	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/164615c0-317b-4d38-983c-74fed048ba39
	Human activities	Military	OSPAR Encounters with Dumped Chemical and Conventional Munitions	OSPAR COMMISSION	ODIMS (OSPAR DATA PORTAL)	http://odims.ospar.org/geoportal/rest/document?id=%7B08306F50-5D21-4C68-9A6F-49AFA0975990%7D
	Human activities	Military	Système d'information et communication (SIC) – Zone de protection	NRW	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/789d506b-13cb-4902-9c20-cadfe483927b
	Human activities	Military	Radars portuaires	Préfectures maritimes	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fre/catalog.search#/metadata/c37cf574-c612-4fae-bbab-dfb2eb028880
	Human activities	Military	Radars de surveillance	Préfectures maritimes	SEXTANT	
✓	Human activities	Raw material extraction	EMODnet Aggregate Extraction Locations	AZTI-TECNALIA	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Aggregate+Extraction
✓	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Recursos Minerais Metálicos (Área potencial Pnodules, PMS, FeMn Crusts)	IPMA	PSOEM Geoportal	http://webgis.dgrm.mam.gov.pt/arcgis/services/PSOEM/Rec_Min_Met_IPMA_EMEPC/MapServer/WMServer?request=GetCapabilities&service=WMS
✓	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Petróleo : area Potencial / areas atribuidas / areas manif interesse	ENMC	PSOEM Geoportal	http://webgis.dgrm.mam.gov.pt/arcgis/rest/services/PSOEM/PSOEM_petroleo2/MapServer/info/me
✓	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Hydrocarbon extraction	COGEA	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Boreholes
✓	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Offshores Installations	COGEA	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Offshore+Installations
✓	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Localisation des forages exploratoires d'hydrocarbures en mer	Ministère de l'Industrie	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportail/sextant#/metadata/425cccc6-ddef-40e7-9a88-a19c50b669c5
✓	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Sand extraction	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Raw material	Hydrocarbon exploration and	CEDEX	CEDEX	

		extraction	exploitation			
✓	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Reserved area for capture and storage of atmospheric carbon	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Reserved area for capture and storage of atmospheric carbon	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Zones d'intérêt (potentiel extractif) en Mer du Nord, Manche et Atlantique.	IFREMER	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportail/sextant#/metadata/82bc9398-d2ea-47cb-b721-c2098adedb96
	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Nascentes_minerais_usos_	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={EDEFADC-5628-4A44-BDFA-07304B256BE1}
	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Crosta FeMn	IPMA		http://webgis.dgrm.mam.gov.pt/arcgis/services/PSOEM/IPMA_FeMnCrusts/MapServer/WMServer?request=GetCapabilities&service=WMS
	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Áreas potenciais mineração		Plano de Situação do Ordenamento do Espaço Marítimo/Mar Português - PSOEM Geoportal	http://webgis.dgrm.mam.gov.pt/arcgis/rest/services/PSOEM/DGEG_areas_potenciais/MapServer/info/metadata
	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Unités d'extraction de granulats marins	IFREMER	SEXTANT	
	Human activities	Raw material extraction	SISMER - Prélèvements de Granulats marins	IFREMER	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/2794d3b6-e9a1-4a4f-b039-a328af9122dc
	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Permis exclusifs de recherche, concessions, casiers, ressources	MEDDE - IFREMER		
	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Port de débarquement de granulats marins			
	Human activities	Raw material extraction	Áreas Estratégicas de Gestão Sedimentar		Plano de Situação do Ordenamento do Espaço Marítimo/Mar Português - PSOEM Geoportal	http://webgis.dgrm.mam.gov.pt/arcgis/rest/services/PSOEM_GEOPORTAL/Area_estrat_gest_sedimentar_APA/MapServer
✓	Human activities	Submarine cable	Cables et conduites	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/csw/ISOAP?service=CSW&version=2.0.2&request=GetRecordById&Id=BDML_CABLES.xml
✓	Human activities	Submarine cable	SIGCables Submarine Cables Routes	COGEA	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=SIGCables+Submarine+Cables+Routes
✓	Human activities	Submarine cable	Telecommunication cables (schematic routes)	COGEA	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Telecommunication+Cables+%28schematic+routes%29
✓	Human activities	Submarine cable	EMODnet Landing stations	COGEA	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Landing+Stations
	Human activities	Submarine cable	Kis orca Subsea Cables	COGEA	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Kis+Orca+Subsea+Cables
	Human activities	Submarine cable	Cables y Tuberias	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Atividades de desportos náuticos dentro da Rede Nacional de Áreas Protegidas	ICNF	SNIMAR Geoportal	http://geoportal.snimar.pt/snimarservices/Values/GetInformacaoMetadados?idMetadados=0dab35d7-e474-4d9f-b4b4-b23d63366dc1
✓	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Praia acessível	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={268B9845-E472-4AD4-902B-C9782C352EA1}
✓	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Marinas	boatlaunch	MMO MARINE PLANNING EVIDENCE	http://mmogis.services.defra.gov.uk/arcgis/rest/services/Recreation_national/MapServer
✓	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Sentier du littoral français	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=546644
✓	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Moorings in marinas	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Hotel beds	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Touristic Vulnerability	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Slipways	boatlaunch	MMO MARINE PLANNING EVIDENCE	http://mmogis.services.defra.gov.uk/arcgis/rest/services/Recreation_national/MapServer
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Points d'intérêt situés à proximité immédiate du sentier du littoral	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=512551

	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Equipements touristiques directement liés au sentier du littoral	DDTM	GEOLITTORAL	
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Sites de baignade du Finistère	DDTM29	GÉOBRETAGNE	http://geobretagne.fr/geonetwork/apps/georchestra/?uuid=e6bcea0c-23c2-42f6-92ab-2f2bc98f64b1
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Bathing Waters	AGÊNCIA PORTUGUESA DO AMBIENTE	SISTEMA NACIONAL INFORMACAO DE AMBIANTE	http://sniamb.apambiente.pt/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?uuid={268B9845-E472-4AD4-902B-C9782C352EA1}
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Establecimientos turísticos	Govern Illes Balears	INFRAESTRUCTURA DE DADES ESPACIALS DE LES ILLES BALEARS	
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Platges i cales	Govern Illes Balears	INFRAESTRUCTURA DE DADES ESPACIALS DE LES ILLES BALEARS	
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Boyas	Govern Illes Balears	INFRAESTRUCTURA DE DADES ESPACIALS DE LES ILLES BALEARS	
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Zones de baignade surveillées	ARS		
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Qualité des eaux de baignade	ARS		
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Sports nautiques	DDTM		
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Thalasso	DDTM		
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Annual overnight stays by province	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Phares			
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	ITP marinas e portos de recreio/Surf		Plano de Situação do Ordenamento do Espaço Marítimo/Mar Português - PSOEM Geoportal	http://webgis.dgrm.mam.gov.pt/arcgis/rest/services/PSOEM/POEM_ITP/MapServer/info/metadata
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Musées maritimes			
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Hébergements	SOES		
	Human activities	Tourism & recreation	Puntos de muestreo Aguas Baño 2017	CEDEX	CEDEX	
✓	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Communes avec des PPRL prescrits	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=546650
✓	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Communes avec des PPRL approuvés	MEEM / CEREMA	GEOLITTORAL	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportal/sextant#/metadata/c1658b52-e2e3-43e4-b185-36e6278c5648
✓	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Hauteurs d'eau	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=367683
✓	Human activities	Coastal Defence	EMODnet - Dredging	AZTI-TECNALIA	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Dredging
✓	Human activities	Coastal Defence	EMODnet Dredge spoil dumping	CETMAR	EMODnet human activities Portal	http://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/search-results.php?dataname=Dredge+Spoil+Dumping+%28Points%29#ID0EADA
✓	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Indicateur national de l'érosion côtière (polygones)	MEEM / CEREMA	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=367700
✓	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Indicateur national de l'érosion côtière (Date)	MEEM / CEREMA	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=367700
✓	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Nombre de catastrophes naturelles liées à la mer par commune	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=367673
✓	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Commune progressant dans l'échelle d'intensité IBC	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=367670
✓	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Indicateur IBC	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=367671
✓	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Zones basses	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=367679
✓	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Coastal Erosion trends	EEA		http://data.adriplan.eu/layers/geonode%3Aerosion_trend
✓	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Dates (indicateur national de l'érosion côtière)	MEEM ; CEREMA	GEOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=367696

	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Imersão de dragados	DGRM	PSOEM Geoportal	
	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Indicateur IB	MEEM	GEOLITTORAL	
	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Communes avec des ppRL non prescrits non approuvés	MEEM	Geoportail	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=546648
	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Commune progressant dans l'échelle d'intensité IB	MEEM	GÉOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=367674
	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Urbanization of the littoral in Andalusia in 1956			http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_evolucion_urbano_costa?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities&
	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Urbanization of the littoral in Andalusia in 2007			http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_evolucion_urbano_costa?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities&
	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Urbanization of the littoral in Andalusia in 1998			http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_evolucion_urbano_costa?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities&
	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Urbanization of the littoral in Andalusia in 2001			http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/mapwms/REDIAM_evolucion_urbano_costa?&service=wms&request=getcapabilities&
	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Submersion marine	MEEM	GÉOLITTORAL	http://www.geocatalogue.fr/Detail.do?id=367668
	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Centre de stockage Polmar	DIRM		
	Human activities	Coastal Defence	Plan de pose de barrage Polmar			
✓	Human activities	Underwater cultural heritage	Epaves et obstructions	Shom	DATA.SHOM.FR	http://services.data.shom.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/BDML_EPAVES.xml
✓	Human activities	Underwater cultural heritage	wrecks	IHM	Geoportal de la Infraestructura de datos espaciales del Instituto Hidrográfico de la Marina	
	Human activities	Underwater cultural heritage	World Heritage Sites	VLIZ	MARINEREGIONS.ORG	http://www.marineregions.org/sources.php#heritage
✓	Human activities	Scientific research	Radioactivity monitoring network	CEDEX	CEDEX	
	Human activities	Scientific research	Lieux d'observation et de surveillance du réseau REMI	NSO	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportail/sextant#/metadata/5626ebc2-709b-4fb1-b369-cda94a565c0d
	Human activities	Scientific research	Lieux d'observation et de surveillance du réseau REPHY	IFREMER	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportail/sextant#/metadata/aa8fe568-d2c0-4b53-a8bb-d9fce2b5293
	Human activities	Scientific research	Radiactivity monitoring network			
	Human activities	Scientific research	Lieux d'observation et de surveillance du réseau REMI	RSL	SEXTANT	http://sextant.ifremer.fr/fr/geoportail/sextant#/metadata/f2788424-04ee-40aa-9c41-8b3b0b3a8274
	Human activities	Scientific research	Valpena	GIS Valpena - CNPMEM		
	Human activities	Scientific research	Rebent	IFREMER		
	Human activities	Scientific research	Remora	IFREMER		
	Human activities	Scientific research	Localisation des prélèvements géologiques et biologiques marins	IFREMER		http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/2794d3b6-e9a1-4a4f-b039-a328af9122dc
	Human activities	Scientific research	Modélisation PREVIMER de vagues en Manche, Gascogne et Méditerranée	IFREMER		http://sextant.ifremer.fr/geonetwork/srv/fr/catalog.search#/metadata/efc6bae6-2f4f-49a2-abfc-e9be72b305ca
	Human activities	Scientific research	Myocean	CEREMA		
	Human activities	Scientific research	CANDHIS			